

**Texts, Contexts, and Scholars:
The Classical Arabic *Maqāma* in Yorubaland, Nigeria.**

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Table of Content

Dedication	v
Acknowledgement	vii
Abstract (English)	ix
Abstrakt (Deutsch)	x
Figures	xi
1 Introduction	1
• The Yoruba-Nigerian Arabic Literary Tradition	2
• <i>Maqāma</i> in the Nigerian Arabic Literary Map	8
• Dramatis Personae	15
• Methods and Sources	25
• Overview of Chapters	28
2 The Scholarly Setting	31
• The Arabic Reading Public	32
• The <i>maqāma</i> and the reading public	38
• “Learn a <i>maqāma</i> and teach it to others”	40
• Investigating (un)translatability	54
• Debates, critiques, and the literary space	60
3 The Public Sphere	63
• “Secret of Life”	64
• Generating friends and foes	67
• <i>Maqāma</i> sociability	70
• Patronage and Propaganda	73
• The Political Economy of the <i>Maqāma</i> : Publishing and Marketing Strategies	79
• The Spiritual Factor: Talismanic Uses of the <i>Maqāma</i>	90
4 Emotional Dimensions	99
• Emotion and the Contexts of Motivation	100
• Traits of emotions	102
• The Language of Emotion	109
• Representing the physical manifestations of emotion	119
• Emotions in the vernacular	122
5 The Old Way	125
• Nigerian <i>Maqāmāt</i> : Structure, Content and Style	126
I. Structure	126
II. Content	132
III. Style	145

• Further Sources	157
I. Entangled Genres	157
II. Rhetoric and Classical Arabic	161
III. Islamic framework	162
IV. Indigenous context	163
V. Sundry matters	164
Conclusion	167
Appendix	171
1. Titles, Settings, and Main Themes in the Nigerian <i>Maqāma</i> Collections	171
1.1 <i>Al-Maqāma al-Awyuwiyya</i> (two episodes)	171
1.2 <i>Maqāmāt al-Ilūrī</i> (fifty episodes)	171
1.3 <i>Maqāmāt Ibn Yūsuf</i> (thirty episodes)	175
1.4 <i>Kiswat al-‘ārī fī maqāmāt ‘Abd al-Bārī</i> (thirty episodes)	177
2. Prayer Texts (derived from the <i>maqāma</i>) in Yorubaland	181
2.1 Text of the <i>Ya Mu’iya</i> prayer from the <i>Ḥarīriyya</i> ’s <i>al-Maqāma al-Dimashqiyya</i> (no. 12)	181
2.2 Prayers in emulation of the <i>Ḥarīriyya</i> ’s <i>Maqāma</i> 12’s <i>Ya Mu’iya</i> from the Nigerian collections.	182
a. From the <i>Yūsufiyya</i> ’s <i>al-Maqāma al-Abiyūkūtawīyya</i> (no. 12)	182
b. From the <i>Kiswa</i> ’s <i>al-Maqāma al-Ṭūghūwiyya</i> (no. 10)	183
3. Sample <i>Maqāmas</i> from the Nigerian collections: Texts and Translations	185
3.1 <i>Al-Maqāma al-Awyuwiyya</i> (The <i>Maqāma</i> of Oyo)	185
3.2 <i>Al-Maqāma al-Fulāniyya</i> (The <i>Maqāma</i> of the Fulani), no. 22 from the <i>Maqāmāt al-Ilūrī</i> .	195
3.3 <i>Al-Maqāma al-Nayjīriyya</i> (The <i>Maqāma</i> of Nigeria), no. 29 from the <i>Maqāmāt ibn Yūsuf</i> .	198
3.4 <i>Al-Maqāma al-Lāghūsiyya</i> (The <i>Maqāma</i> of Lagos), no. 28 from the <i>Kiswat al-‘ārī fī maqāmāt ‘Abd al-Bārī</i> .	206
Glossary	211
Sources and Bibliography	213
- Interviews	213
- Primary Sources	214
- Secondary Sources	215
Curriculum Vitae	243

Dedication

To Abeni, and to Abdullah, Ayman, A'isha, and Asmaa'.

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"الْحَمْدُ لِلَّهِ الَّذِي بِنِعْمَتِهِ تَتِمُّ الصَّالِحَاتُ"

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Abstract (English)

This dissertation focuses on the phenomenon of the modern Arabic *maqāma* indigenous to Nigeria. My study of the Nigerian Arabic *maqāma*, a modern literary form based on the classical model, challenges the widespread notion that the classical Arabic *maqāma* is an outmoded literary genre, no longer a productive and without relevance to current society. I likewise challenge the marginalization of Nigerian and West African Arabic literature in the global corpus of Arabic literature. As current Nigerian *maqāma* writing demonstrates, as well as the local reception of the classical Arabic literary tradition, there has been, and continues to be, a vibrant tradition of Arabic literary production in Nigeria and West Africa. This transdisciplinary study brings to the fore the groundbreaking contributions of the Nigerian Arabic scholarly community to the Arabic literary tradition via the *maqāma*, a classical Arabic literary genre that has its origins in the sixth/tenth-century Arab world. I draw from cultural studies, comparative literature, African studies, and classical Arabic literature to examine four recently written *maqāma* works by four contemporary authors in Arabic from Yorubaland, Nigeria. I examine these works from the perspectives of their socio-cultural functions, emotional dimensions, scholarly engagement, and literary aesthetics.

The analysis shows how the classical Arabic *maqāma* is “nigerianized” in the twenty-first century, along the dimensions of socialization, indigenization, and literariness in its local context. In fact, the *maqāma* occupies a crucial position in the literary and scholarly map of Nigeria. It constitutes an essential part of the Arabic learning curriculum and commands considerable prestige as a genre of high literary repute and as a source of socio-religious appropriation. Over time it has evolved into a symbol of scholarly authority in the Arabic language. I explore how this classical Arabic literary genre functions in Nigerian society and analyze recently disseminated Nigerian *maqāmāt* as perfect *maqāma* prototypes. By comparing the Nigerian *maqāmāt* with the classical models, i.e., the *Maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī* and the *Maqāmāt al-Hamadhānī*, I argue that the Nigerian *maqāmāt* have gained an important place not only within the canon of Arabic literature in West Africa and Nigeria, but also within the global *maqāma* tradition. The *maqāma* is not only a continuous literary endeavor but a living tradition which continues to be written with renewed vigor. The Nigerian *maqāma* therefore challenges prevailing scholarly narratives not only in regard to the *maqāma* genre but in terms of globalizing Arabic literature as a whole.

Abstrakt (Deutsch)

Diese Dissertation befasst sich mit dem Phänomen der in Nigeria heimischen modernen arabischen *maqāma*. Meine Studie über die nigerianisch-arabische *maqāma*, eine moderne literarische Form, die auf dem klassischen Modell basiert, stellt die weit verbreitete Vorstellung in Frage, die klassische arabische *maqāma* sei eine veraltete literarische Gattung, nicht mehr produktiv und ohne Relevanz für die heutige Gesellschaft. Ebenso stelle ich die Marginalisierung der nigerianischen und westafrikanischen arabischen Literatur im globalen Korpus der arabischen Literatur in Frage. Wie die aktuelle nigerianische *maqāma*-Literatur und die dortige Rezeption der klassischen arabischen Literaturtradition zeigen, gab und gibt es in Nigeria und Westafrika eine lebendige Tradition arabischer Literaturproduktion. Diese transdisziplinäre Studie, stellt den bahnbrechenden Beitrag der nigerianischen arabischen Gelehrtengemeinschaft zur arabischen Literaturtradition anhand der *maqāma* in den Fokus, einer klassischen arabischen Literaturgattung, die ihren Ursprung in der arabischen Welt des sechsten/zehnten Jahrhunderts hat. Ich untersuche mit Bezug auf cultural studies, vergleichender Literaturwissenschaft, Afrikanistik und Arabistik vier kürzlich verfasste *maqāma*-Werke von vier zeitgenössischen Autoren in arabischer Sprache aus dem Yorubaland, Nigeria. Diese Werke beleuchte ich unter den Aspekten ihrer soziokulturellen Funktionen, ihrer emotionalen Dimensionen, ihres wissenschaftlichen Engagements und ihrer literarischen Ästhetik.

Die Analyse zeigt, wie die klassische arabische *maqāma* im einundzwanzigsten Jahrhundert "nigerianisiert" wird, und zwar in den Dimensionen ihrer Sozialisierung, Indigenisierung und Literarizität im lokalen Kontext. Tatsächlich behauptet die *maqāma* auf der literarischen und wissenschaftlichen Landkarte Nigerias einen zentralen Platz. Sie ist wesentlicher Bestandteil des arabischen Lehrplans und genießt als Gattung mit hohem literarischem Ansehen und Quelle sozio-religiöser Aneignung erhebliches Prestige. Im Laufe der Zeit hat sie sich zu einem Symbol für die wissenschaftliche Autorität in der arabischen Sprache entwickelt. Ich untersuche, wie diese klassische arabische Literaturgattung in der nigerianischen Gesellschaft funktioniert und analysiere die seit Kurzem zirkulierenden nigerianischen *maqāmāt* als perfekte *maqāma*-Prototypen. Durch den Vergleich der nigerianischen *maqāmāt* mit ihren klassischen Vorbildern, d.h., den *Maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī* und den *Maqāmāt al-Hamadhānī*, argumentiere ich, dass die nigerianischen *maqāmāt* einen wichtigen Platz nicht nur innerhalb des Kanons der arabischen Literatur in Westafrika und Nigeria, sondern auch innerhalb der globalen *maqāma*-Tradition inne haben. Die *maqāma* ist nicht nur ein stetiges Literaturschaffen, sondern eine lebendige Tradition, die mit neuem Impetus fortgeschrieben wird. Die nigerianische *maqāma* unterläuft daher das vorherrschende wissenschaftliche Narrativ nicht nur in Bezug auf das *maqāma*-Genre, sondern auch auf die Globalisierung der arabischen Literatur insgesamt.

Figures

0. (a) Yorubaland in Nigerian Map.	xii
(b) Nigeria in African Map	xii
1. Imam Mas‘ūd Adebayo	17
2. Şāhib al-Qur‘ān and students	20
3. Shaykh ‘Abd al-Bārī’ Adetunji	24
4. A handwritten <i>maqāma</i> lesson note	49
5. A <i>maqāma</i> teaching session	51
6. A Launching Program of Event	74
7. (a) Cover pages of <i>Maqāmāt al-Ilūrī</i> , 6th Edition.	84
(b) Cover pages of <i>Maqāmāt al-Ilūrī</i> , 5th Edition.	84
8. Front and back cover of <i>Kiswat al-‘ārī fī maqāmāt ‘Abd al-Bārī</i>	85
9. Front and back cover of <i>Maqāmāt Ibn Yūsuf</i>	85
10. A public display of Arabic books	88
11. Prayer for wealth and warding off calamity	95
12. Prayer for protection	95
13. Front Cover of the <i>Badā’i’</i>	96
14. Two <i>mushajjari</i> poems	154

Fig. 0a: Yorubaland, Nigeria. (Drawn by the researcher, based on Falola and Usman 2019, p.33).

Fig. 0b: Nigeria in Africa. (Drawn by the researcher based on the template in: geocurrents.info, May 5, 2022).

1

Introduction

I first encountered the *Maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī* (hereafter, *Ḥarīriyya*) in 2004 as a student in an *Ilé kéú* (traditional Arabic school) in Ibadan, Nigeria.¹ The *Ḥarīriyya* was being taught to the senior students in the school but I, as a new student, was not expected to begin learning the *maqāma*. So I didn't actively participate in the learning sessions, but rather joined the other junior students at the *Ḥarīriyya* lesson as “spectators” or, in the words of our instructor, “listeners.” As junior students, we were not expected to follow along with the text, to read the accompanying commentaries, or even to have our own copy of the *Ḥarīriyya*. For about two weeks, I joined the circle of spectators watching and listening passively as the senior students read out loud parts of the *Ḥarīriyya*.

During this time, I visited an uncle who kept a copy of the *Ḥarīriyya* in his living room bookshelf, not only as a decorative object but also as an emblem of scholarly prestige. Displaying a copy of the *Ḥarīriyya* on one's bookshelf signifies, in the traditional Arabic-Islamic setting of Yorubaland,² the height of Arabic learning and points to its possessor's advanced scholarly position. Indeed, the kind and number of Arabic books one has at display in ones home is a measure of ones scholarly prestige as well as a source of admiration from ones peers. Due to my recent acquaintance with the *Ḥarīriyya* in my new *Ilé kéú*, I zoomed on the *Ḥarīriyya* volume in my uncle's living room. Taking the volume off the shelf, I opened it to the episode, which I had recently “listened” to and tried to reread it. To my surprise I was able to comprehend it. I took the book with me to the *Ilé kéú* the next day, and after having

¹ Literally, Arabic school, *Ile keu* is used mostly for semi-formal and informal forms of Arabic schooling where traditional system of Arabic education thrives. Alternative to it is *madrasa*, a term which is used for modern Arabic schools that operates a class-based system with a standard curriculum. For different types of Arabic-Islamic schooling in West Africa, see Louis Brenner, “Two Paradigms of Islamic Schooling in West Africa,” in *Modes de Transmission de La Culture Religieuse En Islam*, ed. Hassan Elboudrari (Cairo: Institut français d'archéologie orientale du Caire, 1993), 159–80.

² Yoruba refers to both the language and people of southwestern and parts of north-central geopolitical zones (Kwara and Kogi) of Nigeria. Albeit, Yoruba, in all its meanings and usages, transcends the geographic spaces mentioned above to include a significant population in Benin and Togo, focus throughout this study is only on the Nigerian Yoruba society. Any mention of “Yoruba” or “Yorubaland” throughout this work therefore dwells on this Nigerian space. For more on Yoruba subgroups, language, dialects, and geography see Aribidesi Adisa Usman and Toyin Falola, *The Yoruba from Prehistory to the Present* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019), 1–27.

sought the permission of my instructor who questioned me out of curiosity about my ability to tackle the *maqāma* as a new student, I was granted permission to be an active participant in the class reading the *Ḥarīriyya*.

My personal journey with the text illustrates well the role that the *maqāma* plays in the vibrant scholarly culture of Yorubaland as a marker of socio-educational prestige. The *maqāma* occupies a pivotal place in modern Yoruba-Nigerian Arabic intellectual history. This dissertation focuses on the functions of the classical Arabic *maqāma* in the Arabic literary and scholarly tradition of Yorubaland, Nigeria, based on the events of the last twenty years, during which the *maqāma* has been reinvigorated and re-popularized in the form of the indigenous Nigerian Arabic *maqāma*. I pose the following questions: How does the *maqāma* serve as a pedagogical tool in Nigerian Yoruba society? What role does the Nigerian Arabic *maqāma* play in the development of the genre itself, the scholarly tradition, and the general situation of Arabic and Islamic studies in Nigeria? This introductory chapter presents an overview of the variables that constitute this study, introducing the context, the texts, and the scholars who participate in the Nigerian *maqāma* literary endeavor. I survey the Arabic-Islamic scholarly and literary foundation of the Yoruba society of Nigeria as it relates to the development of the *maqāma* genre up until the turn of the twenty-first century.

The Yoruba-Nigerian Arabic Literary Tradition

Nigeria has had a reputation for Arabic literary activities long before and after the colonial time (from late nineteenth to mid-twentieth centuries). By the late eighteenth century, when the Sokoto Jihad that led to the establishment of the Sokoto Islamic state occurred,³ Classical Arabic had been flourishing in the region of central Bilād al-Sūdān, today the territories of modern Nigeria, Niger, and Chad, as a language of communication and literacy.⁴ This area witnessed many political and ideological changes over time, and Arabic played significant role at both the administrative and social levels. It was first used, even before Islam had become widespread in the area, as the language of commerce and had penetrated the administration of the empires of the West African region in Old Ghana, Mali, and Songhai.⁵ Arabic served as both the language

³ For more on Sokoto Jihad, Sokoto Islamic government, and the information surrounding the Arabic scholarship there, see: Stephanie Zehnle, *A Geography of Jihad: Sokoto Jihadism and the Islamic Frontier in West Africa*, 1st ed., Zmo-Studien. Studien Des Leibniz-Zentrum Moderner Orient (Boston: De Gruyter, 2019); Murray Last, *The Sokoto Caliphate*, Ibadan History (London: Longmans, 1967); Jennifer Lofkrantz, "Intellectual Discourse in the Sokoto Caliphate: The Triumvirate's Opinions on the Issue of Ransoming, ca. 1810," *The International Journal of African Historical Studies* 45, no. 3 (2012): 385–401.

⁴ Throughout this study, I use Nigeria only in its colonial and postcolonial senses. Otherwise, Central Bilād al-Sūdān is used for the precolonial reference to the region before the colonial partition of the land.

⁵ For more on these empires and the development of Islam during their times see: Micheal A. Gomez, *African Dominion: A New History of Empire in Early and Medieval West Africa* (Ney Jersey: Princeton University Press,

of communication and writing in trade contracts, king lists, administrative documents, and official correspondence. Arabic inscriptions were also used for grave stones during this period, as we see with the tomb of a Muslim king of the old Mali empire, which can be traced to sixteenth century.⁶ Since the early seventh/thirteenth century, Arabic literary activities had been flourishing in West Africa and many literary works can be found in the corpus of local scholars.⁷ Abū Ishāq Ibrāhīm ibn Ya‘qūb al-Dhakwānī al-Kānimī (d. 608/1211 or 609/1212) is the earliest known author composing in Arabic in the region.⁸ The intellectual history of the area is greatly indebted to Arabic both as its medium and as its reservoir.⁹

Arabic first emerged as a written language in the Kanem-Bornu region in the eastern part of West Africa. By the end of fifteenth century, other centers of Arabic and Islamic activities were founded in cities such as Katsina (in the ninth/fifteen century) and Kano (in the tenth/sixteenth century).¹⁰ Activities in these two latter cities started attracting itinerant scholars from other well-established centers of Arabic learning like Timbuktu, Borno, and also from the north African regions, notably the Maghreb.¹¹ Prominent among those itinerant scholars was the Maghribi scholar Muḥammad ibn ‘Abd al-Karīm al-Maghīlī (d. 910/1505) who travelled through the Bilād al-Sūdān, establishing learning centers wherever he visited.¹² The influence of al-Maghīlī’s scholarly itinerary affected not only the northern part of the present Nigeria but also reached the south, even before the expansion of the Sokoto Jihad westward through the

2018); Sébastien Flynn, “The Relationship Between the Ottoman Empire and Kanem-Borno during the Reign of Sultan Murad III” (Master of Arts, Ankara, Turkey., Ihsan Duğramaci Bilkent University, 2015); David C. Conrad, *Empires of the Medieval West Africa: Ghana, Mali, and Songhay*, Great Empires of the Past (New York: Shoreline, 2005); ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn ‘Abd Allāh Sa‘dī and John O. Hunwick, *Timbuktu and the Songhay Empire: al-Sa‘dī’s Ta’rīkh al-Sūdān down to 1613, and Other Contemporary Documents*, Islamic History and Civilization : Studies and Texts, v. 27 (Leiden ; Boston: Brill, 1999).

⁶ John O. Hunwick, “West Africa and the Arabic Language,” *Sudanic Africa* 15 Language in Africa (2004): 135.

⁷ Many of such works are listed in John O. Hunwick, ed., *Arabic Literature of Africa, Volume 2: The Writings of Central Sudanic Africa* (Leiden: Brill, 1995).

⁸ Hunwick, 17–18. Al-Kānimī’s personality is interestingly important to the *maqāma* development in the Bilād al-Sūdān, see below for more.

⁹ Cf. Sayed H. A. Malik, “Arabic, The Muslim Prayers and Beyond” (Inaugural Lecture, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria, 1999), 7–10.

¹⁰ John O. Hunwick, “The Arabic Literary Tradition of Nigeria,” *Research in African Literatures* 28, no. 3 Arabic Writing in Africa (1997): 210–12.

¹¹ Hunwick 1997, 210–11; Muhammad Sani Umar, “Education and Islamic Trends in Northern Nigeria,” *Africa Today* 48, no. 2 (2001): 133–36.

¹² For more on al-Maghīlī, and his views and activities in the Bilād al-Sūdān see: A. A. Batrān, “A Contribution to the Biography of Shaikh Muḥammad Ibn ‘Abd al-Karīm Ibn Muḥammad (‘Umar-A‘mar) al-Maghīlī, al-Tilmisānī,” *Journal of African History* 14, no. 3 (1973): 381–94. For his particular contribution and influence in Nigeria see: Adam Abdullah al-Ilūrī, *al-Imām al-Maghīlī wa-āthāruh fī l-ḥukūmat al-Islāmiyya fī l-qurūn al-wustā fī Nayjīriyā* (Cairo: Maktaba Wahba, 2012); P E Starratt, “Oral History in Muslim Africa: Al-Maghīlī Legends in Kano” (PhD, Michigan, The University of Michigan, 1993); Rasheed A. Raji, “A Monographic Treatment of Al-Maghīlī by Shaykh Adam ‘Abdullah al-Ilori: An Evidence of His Unbiased Islamic Scholarship in West Africa,” in *Ilorin as a Beacon of Learning and Culture in West Africa*, ed. Zakariyau Idree-Oboh Oseni et al. (Ilorin [Nigeria]: UnIlorin Press, 2015), 1–23.

Nupeland¹³ in the nineteenth century. Prior to the Sokoto Jihad, many scholars (teachers and preachers) of Borno, Katsina and of Malian (Songhai) origin had already been present in Yorubaland and, in the words of Razaq D. Abubakre, “contributed to the efflorescence of Islamic learning in Yorubaland.”¹⁴ Islam in Yorubaland is still sometimes even today referred to as *Ēsin Imale* (“the religion of the people of Mali”), in reference to the contributions Songhai preachers made in spreading the religion in the area.¹⁵ During this pre-Sokoto time, although teaching Arabic for reading comprehension flourished, it still was seldom used as a literary language by the indigenous population of Muslims. Arabic instruction was engaged in mainly for religious purposes, and especially for teaching Islam to new converts. Arabic literary works for the purposes of religious induction included commentaries to religious texts, as well as their summaries, abridgements, and versifications for didactic purposes.

During the nineteenth century under Sokoto rule (1804-1903), Arabic occupied a prominent position, and it reached its peak as the official language of the state. Writing activities flourished, especially among the Fodiawas, the family of Shaykh ‘Uthmān ibn Fodio (d. 1232/1817) who founded the Islamic State. Up to five hundred works in Arabic have been attributed to members of the Fodiawa scholarly family alone.¹⁶ In addition to ‘Uthmān ibn Fodio who wrote mainly didactic and religious works to help consolidate Islamic rule, his brother ‘Abdullāh, his son Muḥammad Bello, and his daughter Asmā’ were also prolific authors, whose areas of concentration spanned across a variety of Arabic and Islamic genres and themes.¹⁷ Other notable and productive writers among members of the Sokoto ruling class included the group known as the Wazirs (“the Ministers”) and their followers from other families.¹⁸ Besides comprising the Sokoto political elite, the Wazirs served as the custodians of knowledge and of the history of the Fodiawa family and the Muslim community at large.¹⁹

¹³ This area covers mainly central Nigeria. For more on Nupe and Arabic and Islamic learning in Nigeria, see: H. I. Imam, “al-‘Allāma al-Wazīr Muḥammad al-Turkumānī wa-āthāruhu fī bilād Yawrubā wa-Nūfē,” *Journal of the Nigerian Association of Teachers of Arabic and Islamic Studies* 8 (2005): 110–25.

¹⁴ Razaq ‘Deremi Abubakre, “Stefan Reichmuth’s Wanderings in the Arabized and Islamized Yorubaland,” in *The Piety of Learning: Islamic Studies in Honor of Stefan Reichmuth*, ed. Micheal Kemper and Ralf Elger (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2017), 362.

¹⁵ For the concept of *Imale* and its development in Yoruba socio-religious context, see: Patrick J. Ryan, *Imale: Yoruba Participation in the Muslim Tradition: A Study of Clerical Piety*, Harvard Dissertations in Religion, no. 11 (Missoula, Mont: Scholars Press, 1977).

¹⁶ cf. the list in Hunwick, *ALA II*, 52–149.

¹⁷ Amidu Olalekan Sanni, “From the Intellectual Powerhouse of Ilorin (Nigeria): Elegy in the Work of Adam ‘Abdallāh al-Ilūrī (1917–1992),” in *The Piety of Learning: Islamic Studies in Honor of Stefan Reichmuth*, ed. Micheal Kemper and Ralf Elger (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2017), 55.

¹⁸ Hunwick, “The Arabic Literary Tradition of Nigeria,” 212. Wazirs are like ministers in the Sokoto Islamic state and their position is the next, in importance, to that of the Amir al-Mu’minin, the head of government, for more, see: Last, *The Sokoto Caliphate*, 145–225.

¹⁹ Hunwick, *ALA II*, 150–51. see also pages 184-185.

As Sokoto rule expanded territorially in the nineteenth century, new learning centers of Arabic were established in the Northern Nigerian cities like Zaria and Kaduna. Although Arabic learning was upheld at these learning centers, they did not bring about widespread written literacy in Arabic. Shaykh ‘Uthmān and his family remained the dominant producers of Arabic literary and religious works in the region. Nevertheless, many works were produced by scholars whose interest also lay in didactic and religious matters. As Sokoto rule spread westward to Nupeland and thereafter to Yorubaland, the Yoruba center of Ilorin, strategically located at the crossroads between the north and the west, rose as an important center of learning towards the end of nineteenth and the beginning of the twentieth centuries.²⁰ The Emirate of Ilorin was annexed to the Gwandu province of the Sokoto in the first half of the nineteenth century, and continued to serve as an important meeting place for scholars from the north and those from the south seeking religious education.²¹ Scholars from northern Nigeria and Nupe land began migrating westward to other parts of Yorubaland as well, and a strong teaching tradition developed there which likewise spawned Arabic literary activities.

With the end of the Sokoto period and the onset of European colonial rule, the status of Arabic began decline in the central Bilād al-Sūdān. Arabic lost its official status as it was replaced with the languages of the colonial masters, English and French. Nonetheless, Arabo-Islamic teaching and learning traditions continued to flourish in the hands of private scholars. In fact, Nigerian scholars, primarily those from the north, countered the colonial challenge by more rigorously upholding Islamic learning and propagating the virtues of Islam. Instead of being totally eclipsed by English and French, Arabic only shifted from the public to the private sphere. Colonial educators responded by incorporating Arabic and Islamic studies into their educational plan.²²

²⁰ For more on Ilorin and its role in the Islamic and Arabic learning in Yorubaland see: Sakariyau Alabi Aliyu, “Transmission of Learning in Modern Ilorin: A History of Islamic Education, 1897-2012” (PhD diss., Leiden, Universiteit Leiden, 2015); Amidu Olalekan Sanni, “The Story of an Autochthonous Scholarly Network: Ilorin and the Making of Modern Ulama in Nigeria” (3rd Annual Public Lecture of the Centre for Ilorin Studies (CILS) of the University of Ilorin, Ilorin [Nigeria], 2015); Stefan Reichmuth, “Literary Culture and Arabic Manuscripts in 19th-Century Ilorin,” in *The Trans-Saharan Book Trade: Manuscript Culture, Arabic Literacy and Intellectual History in Muslim Africa*, ed. Graziano Krätli and Ghislaine Lydon, Libraries of the Written World 8, The Manuscript World 3 (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2011), 213–40; Stefan Reichmuth, *Islamische Bildung und soziale Integration in Ilorin (Nigeria) seit ca.1800* (Münster: LIT-Verlag, 1998). On Arabic and learning dimensions of Ilorin Islamic heritage in contemporary time, see the important articles in: Zakariyau I. Oseni et al., eds., *Ilorin as a Beacon of Learning and Culture in West Africa* (Ilorin [Nigeria]: UnIlorin Press, 2015).

²¹ cf. Musa A. Ajetunmobi, “Islamic Scholars of Ilorin and Their Place in Yorubaland,” *Journal of the Institute of Muslim Minority Affairs* 12, no. 1 (1991): 135–47.

²² Mallam M. Bashir Abubakar, “Muslim Responses to British Colonialism in Northern Nigeria as Expressed in Fulfulde Poems,” *Islamic Africa* 4, no. 1 (2013): 1–14. Cf. also how Muslims respond to colonial education in Ilorin and how they try not only to privatize the Islamic knowledge but also maintain its public position through the colonial strategies, they rebuke the colonial system while they adopt some of its strategies to disseminate Arabic and Islamic education, see: Sakariyau Alabi Aliyu, “The Post-Colonial State and Islamic Education in Ilorin,” *The Annual Review of Islam in Africa* 14 (2017): 77–86.

In Yorubaland, local scholars and their students established private Arabic schools, thus advancing Arabic learning, and producing many accomplished authors as well as passing on Arabo-Islamic heritage to the younger generations. Arabic became an academic language as well as the first written language in Yoruba society to preserve historical and administrative works.²³ Furthermore, academic exchange between Nigeria and many Arab countries from the middle of twentieth century played an important role in advancing the knowledge of Arabic among Nigerians. By sending native speakers to teach in Nigerian Arabic schools and granting scholarships to Nigerians to study in Arab countries like Egypt, Lebanon, Libya, Saudi Arabia, and Syria, academic exchange provided further training and expertise in Arabic learning, making it possible for a new generation of scholars to contribute to the Arabic-Islamic scholarly and literary tradition of Nigeria.²⁴

Modern Arabic literature of the nineteenth to twentieth century remained largely indebted to the classical tradition of the previous centuries in terms of genre, style, and themes. Poetry continues to be the most patronized genre of Arabic literature in Nigeria. Even today Nigerian scholars prize highly the ability to compose elegant Arabic poetry, a pursuit in which Nigerian Arabists excel. As in the past, poetry continues to be composed for a variety of purposes and contexts, whether they be social, religious, or literary. Nigerian scholars employ verse as a medium for religious knowledge in the form of poetic abridgment, commentary, and versification. Poems likewise serve as a format to narrate historical events and recount political activities. In addition to composing verse in classical Arabic literary forms, such as the *rithā'* (elegy), *madīḥ* (eulogy), and *hijā'* (satire), much contemporary poetry touches upon contemporary issues and social concerns. Arabic schools such as the Markaz al-Ta'lim al-'Arabī al-Islāmī in Agege Lagos (hereafter, Markaz) and its affiliates, organize poetry contests, the winners of which are given the honor of being the school's poet laureate. These activities promoting poetry in Arabic schools have encouraged many young students and scholars to produce and publish collections of their poetry.

The prominence of poetry in Nigeria, however, does not overshadow prose. However, most prose works by Nigerian scholars before the last decade of the twentieth century were not

²³ For example, Arabic was used as a language of communication in the palace of Ibadan during this time, see: Isaac Adejoju Ogunbiyi and Stefan Reichmuth, "Arabic Papers from the Olubadan Chancery II: Toying with the Caliphate," *Sudanic Africa* 9 (1998): 135–61; Isaac Adejoju Ogunbiyi and Stefan Reichmuth, "Arabic Papers from the Olubadan Chancery I: A Rebellion of the Ibadan Chieftains or, at the Origins of Yoruba Arabic Prose," *Sudanic Africa* 8 (1997): 109–35.

²⁴ For background information on this and the contribution of the graduates of Arab universities in Nigeria to socio-cultural development in Yorubaland see: Ibrahim Lere Ameen, "Interculturalism in the Writings of Yoruba Graduates of Arab Universities, 1964-2012" (PhD thesis, Nigeria, University of Ibadan, 2014).

of a literary nature but of an academic and nonfiction nature:²⁵ *al-nathr al-ta'limī* as opposed to *al-nathr al-fannī*,²⁶ or “research prose” to use John Hunwick’s term.²⁷ In the last decade of the twentieth century, there has been a shift in the kind of Arabic literary works Nigerians produce. Greater attention is given to prose, such as plays, novels, short stories, and epistolary writings, genres drawn from both modern and classical genres of Arabic literature. While plays, novels and short stories are modern genres, works categorized as *al-dhahabiyyāt* follow the format of Abū al-Qāsim Maḥmūd ibn ‘Umar al-Zamakhsharī’s (d. 538/1144) *Aṭwāq al-dhahab*,²⁸ the outstanding example of the classical Arabic *maqāma* genre, which in turn was based on the models of the *Ḥarīriyya* and the *Maqāmāt al-Hamadhānī* (hereafter, *Hamadhāniyya*). The Arabic *maqāma* is the focus of this study.²⁹

²⁵ Some works of drama later published in the 1990s claim to have been written at least before the middle of twentieth century. However, these are mainly works which were adapted from Qur’anic stories and Islamic historical accounts and should not be seen as a distinctive creative innovation of their authors. This I have explored elsewhere, arguing that even if there are ideas of writing Arabic drama in Nigeria before nineties of the twentieth century, it was not for literary, but for didactic, motives. See my article: Sulaiman Adewale Alagunfon, “Drama in Its Own Way: A Genealogy of Arabic Playwriting in Nigeria,” *Journal of the Nigerian Association of Teachers of Arabic and Islamic Studies* 20 (2017): 52–64.

²⁶ For more on the development of prose works in Nigeria, especially in its academic form see: Kabir Adam Tudun-Nufawa, *al-Nathr al-‘Arabī al-Nayjīrī: ṣuwaruh wa khaṣā’iṣuh ‘abr al-‘uṣūr* (Kano [Nigeria]: Dar al-Ummah, 2011).

²⁷ This term, introduced by John Hunwick, refers to prose works written for the purpose of research and teaching in its traditional sense; see: Hunwick, “The Arabic Literary Tradition of Nigeria,” 217.

²⁸ For whom see: Azmi Yuksel, “Al-Zamakhsharī’s Life and a Critical Edition of His *Dīwān*” (PhD Thesis, Durham, Durham University, 1979).; and for the work see: Dionisius A. Agius, “Some Bib-Bibliographical Notes on Abū ‘l-Qāsim Maḥmūd b. ‘Umar al-Zamakhsharī,” *Al-‘Arabiyya* 15 (1982): 112.

²⁹ For more on Arabic literary writing of Nigerians, especially in the Yoruba society, see: Razaq ‘Deremi Abubakre, *The Interplay of Arabic and Yoruba Cultures in South Western Nigeria* (Iwo [Nigeria]: Darul-Ilm, 2004); Amidu Olalekan Sanni, “Oriental Pearls from Southern Nigeria—Arabic Scholarship in Yorubaland: A Case Study in Acculturation,” *Islamic Studies* 34, no. 4 (1995): 427–50; M. Oloyede Abdul-Rahmon, “A Thematic and Stylistic Study of Arabic Poetry in Ibadan” (PhD, Ibadan [Nigeria], University of Ibadan, 1989); Razaq ‘Deremi Abubakre, “The Contribution of the Yoruba to Arabic Literature” (PhD, London, University of London, 1980). See also the non-exhaustive list of works and authors in: Hunwick, *ALA II*, 439–549; Reichmuth, *Islamische Bildung*.

***Maqāma* in the Nigerian Arabic Literary Map**

Maqāma has variously been translated as session, assembly,³⁰ standing,³¹ séance,³² and most recently by Michael Cooperson, as imposture.³³ The *maqāma* can technically be defined as an anecdote-like form of narrative, whose story revolves around the adventures of a *baṭal* (protagonist), written in mostly a sophisticated style of *sajʿ* (rhyme) prose, embellished with *shiʿr* (poem), and often recounted by a witnessing *rāwī* (narrator).³⁴ Against the backdrop of numerous “misrepresentations” that the *maqāma* as a literary genre has witnessed over time,³⁵ Jaakko Hämeen-Anttila identifies its three most important features as “a fictitious *isnād* (or, at least, an implicitly fictitious scene of narration), a fictitious hero (often, but not always, accompanied by a fictitious narrator who may use the name of the author) and, finally, the use of *sajʿ*.”³⁶ These three components of the *maqāma* distinguish it from other literary genres. The *maqāma*’s protagonist, for instance, usually disguises himself, adopting various different postures, to borrow a term from Michael Cooperson.³⁷ A *maqāma*’s protagonist may show up as a renowned business tycoon who trades in uncommon commodities in one episode, and in another episode, he takes on the persona of a legal luminary who has mastered the intricacies of the law. Other times he poses as a medical doctor whose praxis never fails to heal, or as a successful teacher of language, a master of punning, and a linguistic acrobat.

³⁰ Cf. Thomas Chenery and Francis Steingass’ use of the word, which has been extensively adopted by later scholars, see: Francis Joseph Steingass, *The Assemblies of al-Ḥarīrī: Translated from the Arabic with Notes, Historical and Grammatical*, vol. 2, 2 vols. (London: The Royal Asiatic Society, 1898); T. Chenery, F.J. Steingass, and F. Arbuthnot, *The Assemblies of al-Ḥarīrī: Translated from the Arabic, with an Introduction, and Notes Historical and Grammatical*, Oriental Translation Fund: New Series, v. 9 (Williams and Norgate, 1867).

³¹ Some scholars adopt this and used it to mean the opposite of *majlis* (lit. sitting, or sitting place) literature of which was also common in premodern times. For more on *majlis* literature see: Samer M. Ali, *Arabic Literary Salons in the Islamic Middle Ages: Poetry, Public Performance, and the Presentation of the Past*, Poetics of Orality and Literacy (Notre Dame, Ind: University of Notre Dame Press, 2010).

³² For French translation of *Ḥarīriyya* see: Abu Muhammad al-Ḥarīrī, *Les Séances de Hariri, Traduction Française Par Venture de Paradis*, ed. Attia Amer (Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksel, 1964); Abu Muhammad al-Ḥarīrī, *Les Séances de Hariri, Publiées En Arabe, Avec Un Commentaire Choisi*, ed. Silvester de Sacy (Paris: Imprimerie Royale, 1822).

³³ Michael Cooperson notes that he chose to translate *maqāma* with the word *imposture* because “it conveys both the substance of Abū Zayd’s activities ... and the embodied character of the Arabic word (standing being a kind of posture)” see the footnote 4: Michael Cooperson, “Introduction,” in *Impostures*, by Ḥarīrī, trans. Michael Cooperson, Library of Arabic Literature (New York: New York University Press, 2020), xix–xl.

³⁴ Most translations of the *maqāma* take cognizance of two things: what the word *maqāma* “means” in its literary sense or what it “does,” cf. the analysis of: Michael Cooperson, “Notes on Translation,” in *Impostures*, by Ḥarīrī, trans. Michael Cooperson, Library of Arabic Literature (New York: New York University Press, 2020), xxix–xl.

³⁵ Based on the misrepresentations, many works have been erroneously considered as belonging to the genre of *maqāma* and vice-versa. For more on this, see: Jaakko Hämeen-Anttila, “An Old-Fashioned Genre – *Maqāma* in the 18th Century,” *Rocznik Orientalistyczny* 65, no. 2 (2012): 6.

³⁶ Hämeen-Anttila, 6–7.

³⁷ Cooperson, “Introduction.” xi

The Arabic *maqāma* is structured according to several components.³⁸ It begins with an *isnād*, a chain of narration usually beginning with the narrator who relates the story of a protagonist. Following the *isnād* is a general introduction, which explains the narrator's relationship to the context of the *maqāma* or episode to be narrated. The general introduction normally ends with a vocal link, which shifts the attention to the main story.³⁹ The link explains how the narrator came to learn of the hero's adventure. Next is the main story, which Hämeen-Anttila refers to as an episode, in which the hero takes center stage, and which also contains a recognition scene, an envoi, and a finale. In the recognition scene, the hero, the narrator, and perhaps the audience, all properly meet and recognize one another. The envoi comprises "a short quotation of verses... which sums up the philosophy and explains ... (hero's) behaviour, ... or identifies him, being thus part of the recognition scene."⁴⁰ The finale⁴¹ is a concluding statement explaining how the meeting between the two important characters (narrator and protagonist) ends.

The *maqāma* generally alternates between storytelling, scenes that are reminiscent of the modern play, and sermon-like homilies. It parodies the *ḥikāya* (narrative) and the *qiṣṣa* (story telling),⁴² and has been recently linked to *khayāl al-ẓill* (shadow play),⁴³ in fact, *maqāma* stories were performed by early shadow play dramatists.⁴⁴ The *maqāma* covers a wide range of themes such as philology, comic tales, and social criticism.⁴⁵ Whether what *maqāmas* narrate maybe labelled fictional or realistic remains unresolved among scholars, especially when placed in comparison and in relation to the modern Arabic novel.⁴⁶ Since the *maqāma* is made of largely unconnected episodes, it is possible that some of them may be realistic. This can be

³⁸ For the sequential list of the *maqāma* structure see: Jaakko Hämeen-Anttila, *Maqāma: A History of a Genre*, Diskurse Der Arabistik, Bd. 5 (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2002), 45–52.

³⁹ Hämeen-Anttila, 50.

⁴⁰ Hämeen-Anttila, 51.

⁴¹ Hämeen-Anttila, 51.

⁴² Abdelfattah Kilito, *al-Maqāmāt: al-sard wa-l-ansāq al-thaqāfiyya*, trans. 'Abd-al-Kabīr aš-Sharqāwī, 2nd ed. (Casablanca: Dār Tūbqāl, 2001), 131–42; Philip F. Kennedy, "The *Maqāmāt* as a Nexus of Interests: Reflections on Abdelfattah Kilito's 'Les Séances,'" in *Writing and Representation in Medieval Islam: Muslim Horizons*, ed. Julia Bray (London and New York: Routledge, 2006), 161–67.

⁴³ Alain F. George, "The Illustration of the *Maqāmāt* and the Shadow Play," *Muqarnas* 28 (2011): 1–42.; David J. Roxburgh, "In Pursuit of Shadows: Al-Ḥarīrī's *Maqāmāt*," *Muqarnas* 30 (2013): 171–212.

⁴⁴ See: George, "The Illustration of the *Maqāmāt* and the Shadow Play," 1. For more on the performativity and theatricality of the *maqāma*, see: Keiji Okazaki, "*Maqāma* as a Courtroom Play - Disguised Hero, Dupe Judge," *Orient* 42 (2007): 125–49.

⁴⁵ Cf. the *maqāma* subgenres in: Hämeen-Anttila, *Maqāma*, 55–61.

⁴⁶ See: Jaakko Hämeen-Anttila, "The Novel and the *Maqāma*," in *The Oxford Handbook of Arab Novelistic Traditions*, ed. Wail S. Hassan (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017), 89–102; Mohamed-Salah Omri, "Local Narrative Form and Constructions of the Arabic Novel," *Novel: A Forum on Fiction* 41, no. 2/3 (2008): 244–63. See also: Mohamed-Salah Omri, "'There's a Jahiz for Every Age': Narrative Construction and Intertextuality in al-Hamadhānī's *Maqāmāt*," *Arabic and Middle Eastern Literatures* 1, no. 1 (1998): 31–46. See also: Max Robert Shmookler, "The Levantine *Maqāma* Before the *Nahda* and Beyond the Novel" (PhD diss., New York, Columbia University, 2020).

said of classical *maqāmāt*, but it is more conspicuous in later *maqāma* works which clearly include stories that depict social reality.⁴⁷

Arising in fourth/tenth-century Iran, most scholars agree that the *maqāma* originated with the eleventh-century scholar and author, Abū al-Faḍl Badī' al-Zamān Aḥmad ibn al-Ḥusayn al-Hamadhānī (358-398/968-1008),⁴⁸ even though some believe that he might have created the *maqāma* in emulation of, or borrowing from, earlier “similar” works,⁴⁹ such as Ibn Durayd al-Azdī's (d. 321/933) *Aḥādīth*, *Amālī* of Ibn Durayd's disciple Abū 'Alī al-Qālī (d. 356/967)⁵⁰ or the *Qaṣaṣ al-nahār wa-samar al-layl* by Hamadhānī's teacher Aḥmad ibn Fāris (d. 395/1005).⁵¹ In any case, the *maqāma* developed and spread to the Muslim East and West and left indelible marks not only in literature but also in culture, arts,⁵² and education. It transcended the Arabo-Islamic realm to enter the Spanish,⁵³ Hebrew,⁵⁴ Persian⁵⁵ and Turkish⁵⁶ literary traditions.

Al-Hamadhānī and his prominent emulator, Abū Muḥammad al-Qāsim ibn 'Alī al-Ḥarīrī (446-516/1054-1122), are the best-known creators of the *maqāma*. Both have spurred a

⁴⁷ For more on fictionality and the *maqāma* see: Rina Drory, *Models and Contacts: Arabic Literature and Its Impact on Medieval Jewish Culture* (Leiden: Brill, 2000), 11–33; Rina Drory, “Fiction, Medieval,” in *EAL*, 1998; Rina Drory, “Three Attempts to Legitimize Fiction in Classical Arabic Literature,” *Jerusalem Studies in Arabic and Islam* 18 (1994): 146–64; Fedwa Malti-Douglas, “*Maqāmāt* and *Adab: al-Maqāma al-Maḍriyya* of al-Hamadhānī,” *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 105, no. 2 (1985): 249–51.

⁴⁸ Kennedy, “The *Maqāmāt* as a Nexus of Interests: Reflections on Abdelfattah Kilito's ‘Les Séances,’” 153; Devin J. Stewart, “The *Maqāma*,” in *Arabic Literature in the Post-Classical Period*, ed. Roger Allen and D. S. Richards, *The Cambridge History of Arabic Literature* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006), 145; Kilito, *al-Maqāmāt: al-sard wa-l-ansāq al-thaqāfiyya*, 5; A.F.L. Beeston, “Al-Hamadhānī, al-Ḥarīrī and the *Maqāmāt* Genre,” in *Abbasid Belles Lettres*, ed. Julia Ashtiany et al. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990), 127.

⁴⁹ Arguments on both sides can be found in: J. N. Mattock, “The Early History of the *Maqāma*,” *Journal of Arabic Literature* 15 (1984): 1–18; A. F. L. Beeston, “The Genesis of the *Maqāmāt* Genre,” *Journal of Arabic Literature* 2 (1971): 1–12.

⁵⁰ Beeston, “The Genesis of the *Maqāmāt* Genre,” 1–2.

⁵¹ Maurice A. Pomerantz and Bilal W. Orfalī, “Ibn Fāris and the Origins of the *Maqāma* Revisited,” in *Arabic Belles Lettres*, ed. Joseph E. Lowry and Shawkat M. Toorawa, *Resources in Arabic and Islamic Studies* 10 (Atlanta, GA: Lockwood Press, 2019), 95–114.

⁵² Note that al-Ḥarīrī's *Maqāmāt* are among the most frequently illustrated works, see: al-Qāsim Ibn-'Alī al-Ḥarīrī and Yaḥyā Ibn-Maḥmūd al-Wāsiṭī, *Maqāmāt Al-Hariri Illustrated By Y. Al-Wasiti. 13th Century Arabic manuscript*, ed. Oleg Grabar, Facsimile ed (London: Touch@rt, 2003).

⁵³ Douglas C. Young, *Rogues and Genres: Generic Transformation in the Spanish Picaresque and Arabic Maqāma* (Newark, Delaware: Juan de la Cuesta, 2004); Rina Drory, “The *Maqāma*,” in *The Literature of Al-Andalus*, ed. Maria Rosa Menocal, Raymond P. Scheindlin, and Micheal Sells, *Cambridge History of Arabic Literature* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000), 190–210; Jareer Abu-Haidar, “*Maqāmāt* Literature and the Picaresque Novel,” *Journal of Arabic Literature* 5 (1974): 1–10.

⁵⁴ Naoya Katsumata, “The Style of the *Maqāma*: Arabic, Persian, Hebrew, Syriac,” *Arabic and Middle Eastern Literatures* 5, no. 2 (2002): 117–37; Drory, *Models and Contacts: Arabic Literature and Its Impact on Medieval Jewish Culture*.

⁵⁵ Jaakko Hämeen-Anttila, “Muḥammad 'Awfi and the Persian *Maqāma*,” *Rocznik Orientalistyczny* 64, no. 1 (2011): 52–59; Vahid Behmardi, “The Maḍīrah of Baghdād versus the Sikbāj of Nishapur: The Migration of a *Maqāma* from Arabic to Persian,” in *Poetry's Voice-- Society's Norms: Forms of Interaction between Middle Eastern Writers and Their Societies*, ed. Barbara Winckler and Andreas Pflitsch, *Literaturen Im Kontext*, v. 24 (Wiesbaden: Reichert, 2006), 95–104; Katsumata, “The Style of the *Maqāma*: Arabic, Persian, Hebrew, Syriac.”

⁵⁶ Hulūsi Kiliç, “El-Makāmāt,” in *Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı İslâm Ansiklopedisi* (Üsküdar: Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı, 2013).

slew of imitators and readers which survive until today. Specifically, al-Ḥarīrī's *maqāma* has come to serve as a standard genre of “everything” Arabic and thus occupies a very important position in the learning, teaching, and writing of Arabic, even beyond the Arab world. Its influence in Nigeria is noteworthy and has prompted the present study.

The work of the late twelfth-century poet and grammarian, al-Kānimī, best exemplifies the influence and position of the *maqāma* in the central Bilād al-Sūdān, when Arabic first came to be used as a literary language in the region in the late medieval period. Al-Kānimī's *Ta'liqāt 'alā maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī*, composed in the final decade of the sixth/twelfth century when al-Kānimī moved to the Marrakesh,⁵⁷ is considered the oldest *maqāma* commentary to be produced by a native from the region of the central Bilād al-Sūdān, as discovered by Hunwick.⁵⁸

Although the work is no longer extant, fragments of the *Ta'liqāt* have been preserved by Muḥammad ibn 'Abd al-Malik al-Marrākushī (d. 703/1303), who claims to have copied parts of it directly from al-Kānimī's autograph manuscript copy.⁵⁹ Although al-Kānimī was not the first scholar known from the region (he was trained by indigenous scholars of the area),⁶⁰ no record of written works exist in the region before him.⁶¹ Al-Kānimī's work shows herein the extent to which West African scholars engaged with the *maqāma* beginning in the sixth/twelfth century.

Scholarly engagement with the *maqāma* continued in the subsequent centuries. In particular, scholars adopted the “*maqāma* style.” This can be seen in their use of *saj'* (rhymed prose), which become commonplace in their works. Although, *saj'* has earlier precedence in classical Arabic literature, the writers of *maqāmāt* developed it to its fullest extent, transforming it into a sophisticated style which served as a model for *maqāma* and non-*maqāma* prose writing alike.⁶² Classical works of Arabic literature continue to serve as models for Nigerian scholars engaged in Arabic literary production.⁶³

⁵⁷ Al-Kānimī was reported to have migrated to Marrakesh in 594AH as part of a diplomatic mission from Kanem, see: Bencherifa, *Ibrāhīm al-Kānimī (m. 609h/1212-1213), figure, illustre dans les relations culturelles entre le Maroc et Bilād al-Sūdān*, 19. For more on al-Kānimī, see: Ousmane Oumar Kane, *Beyond Timbuktu: An Intellectual History of Muslim West Africa* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2016), 43–44; Hunwick, *ALA II*, 17–19; Mohammed Bencherifa, *Ibrāhīm al-Kānimī (m. 609h/1212-1213), figure, illustre dans les relations culturelles entre le Maroc et Bilād al-Sūdān* (Rabat: Institut des Etudes Africaines, Université Mohammed V, 1991); Abduh Badawi, *al-Shu'arā' al-sūd wa-khaṣā'ishuhum fī l-shi'r al-'Arabī* (Cairo: al-Maṭba'a al-Miṣriyya, 1973), 277–78.

⁵⁸ Hunwick, *ALA II*, 19.

⁵⁹ Bencherifa, 18; al-Marrākushī Ibn 'Abd 'l-Malik, *al-Dhayl wa-l-takmila li kitābay al-mawṣūl wa-l-ṣila*, ed. Iḥsān Abbās, Mohammed Bencherifa, and Bashār Marouf, vol. 2 (Tunis: Dār 'l-Gharb 'l-Islāmī, 2012), 52.

⁶⁰ Badawi, *al-Shu'arā' al-sūd wa-khaṣā'ishuhum fī l-shi'r al-'Arabī*, 277.

⁶¹ Hunwick, *ALA II*, 19.

⁶² Many scholars on *maqāma* agree that the most distinctive feature of *maqāma* is rhyme prose, this made some to consider the *Hamadhāniyya* as the first attempt to thoroughly use *saj'* for literacy purpose, cf. for instance the usage of *saj'* before the time of al-Hamadhānī in: Mattock, “The Early History of the *Maqāma*.”

⁶³ Sanni, “Oriental Pearls”; Abubakre, *The Interplay of Arabic and Yoruba Cultures in South Western Nigeria*.

The influence of the *maqāma* on Nigerian authors can be seen in two areas: the adoption of *maqāma* style of *sajʿ* and, more conspicuously, the direct adaptation and use of *maqāma* vocabulary. This can be seen in the writings of ʿAbdullāh ibn Fodio (d. 1245/1829) and Muḥammad Bello ibn ʿUthmān ibn Fodio (d. 1253/1837) who used the *maqāma* style in their works.⁶⁴ This is not unexpected, because as at the time of the Fodiawas, the *Ḥarīriyya* had become an important part of the curriculum, if not the most important, for lexicological studies.⁶⁵ Although, the curriculum for Arabic and Islamic learning was dominated by religious works, the *maqāma*, together with the *Muthallathāt Quṭrub* of Abū ʿAlī Muḥammad b. Aḥmad al-Mustanīr Quṭrub (d. 206/821), an early Arabic grammarian and linguist whose work is on triplets of similar-looking words with different meanings, occupies the little space given to lexicology in the Arabic pedagogy of the region.⁶⁶

Throughout the twentieth century, the *maqāma*'s prestige increased among Yoruba scholars. It emerged as a major authoritative Arabic text, the mastery of which imparted high status due to high proficiency in Arabic. To “know” the *maqāma*, especially in modern Yoruba society, became synonymous to being a polymath of Arabic knowledge which entailed a high status of authority in society. Today reputable scholars of Arabic in Nigeria claim to have expertise in the *Ḥarīriyya* and other *maqāma* works, like those of al-Hamadhānī, al-Zamakhsharī and Nāṣif al-Yāzījī (d. 1871). The *maqāma* represents the “apex of the curriculum” to borrow a phrase from Stefan Reichmuth.⁶⁷

If what is available on the market shapes what people read in contemporary society, one can say that the popularity of al-Ḥarīrī's work continues today, even though Nigerians are now conversant with many other *maqāmāt* available to them in the market. An examination of the

⁶⁴ For more on the influence of *maqāma* in the writings of Nigerian scholars, see: Barihi Adetunji, “Dirāsa naqdiyya li-maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī wa-āthāruhā fī l-adab al-ʿarabī al-nayjirī” (PhD thesis, Ilorin [Nigeria], University of Ilorin, 2004).

⁶⁵ See the work of Abdullah ibn Fodio who mentions, in his *Īdāʿ al-nusūkh man akhadhtu ʿanhu min al-shuyūkh, Maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī* as part of the texts they used to study during their time, see: Mervyn Hiskett, “Material Relating to the State of Learning among the Fulani before Their Jihād,” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 19, no. 3 (1957): 565. cf. also Abdullah b. Abī Bakr al-Burtalī, *Fath al-Shakūr fī maʿrifat al-ʿulamāʾ bilād al-Takrūr*, ed. Muḥammad Ibrāhīm al-Kattānī and Muḥammad Ḥajjī (Beirut: Dār al-Gharb al-Islāmī, 1981), 32.

⁶⁶ Bruce S Hall and Charles C. Stewart, “The Historic ‘Core Curriculum’ and the Book Market in Islamic West Africa,” in *The Trans-Saharan Book Trade: Manuscript Culture, Arabic Literacy and Intellectual History in Muslim Africa*, ed. Graziano Krätli and Ghislaine Lydon, vol. 3, Libraries of the Written World 8, The Manuscript World (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2011), 121. On Quṭrub see: G. Troupeau, “Quṭrub, the Cognomen of Abū ʿAlī Muḥammad b. al-Mustanīr,” in *EP*, n.d. For *muthallath* and its later reception, see: Beatrice Gruendler, “Stability and Change in Arabic Script,” in *The Shape of Script: How and Why Writing Systems Change*, ed. Stephen D. Houston, 1st ed, School for Advanced Research Advanced Seminar Series (Santa Fe, N.M: School for Advanced Research Press, 2012), 113–17.

⁶⁷ Reichmuth, *Islamische Bildung*. see also the review of the work for important comment on the position of the classics, Amidu Olalekan Sanni, “Review of Islamische Bildung Und Soziale Integration in Ilorin (Nigeria) Seit ca. 1800 by Stefan Reichmuth,” *Journal of African History* 41, no. 2 (2000): 316–18.

book market that I did in early 2018 for the major towns of Yorubaland, like Ilorin and Ibadan, reveals a brisk trade in the *Ḥarīriyya* due to high demand, as the many copies that I identified demonstrate. It is interesting to note that while the copies of al-Ḥarīrī's work were printed in the Arab world, the copies of al-Hamadhānī's and al-Yāzījī's *maqāmāt* were reproduced locally by using old editions in the hands of publishers who relied on local printers to produce more copies. This phenomenon of local interest in other *maqāmāt* may imply a higher demand for them, but it also could alternatively mean that printing them in this way was just an easier and less expensive source of books for the local book trade in Nigeria, since importing books is much more expensive than local production. The reputation attached to internationally produced books, especially regarding how Nigerian *maqāmāt* are published, will be discussed later in Chapter Three.

The *maqāma* genre in Nigeria also has social and educational dimensions. As thoroughly explored in Chapters Two and Three, the *maqāma*, especially the *Ḥarīriyya*, continues to be an important vehicle of Arabic learning in Yorubaland. The *maqāma* likewise gradually penetrated the social circles of the Nigerian ulama which has led to greater social acceptance for the culture of the *maqāma*. For instance, the term *saruji* (locally adopted as synonymous to cleverness, cunning, trickery), derived from the name of al-Ḥarīrī's hero in his *Maqāmāt*, has come to be socially accepted and adopted for various social activities. The *saruji* as a Nigerian social phenomenon is thoroughly explored in Chapter Three.

The twenty-first century opens with a new phase in the Nigerians' engagement with the *maqāma* genre. Scholars, at this time, move beyond imitating the classical works of *maqāmāt* in their writings of other genres, began to produce their very own *maqāmāt* in Arabic. Although it is impossible to know with complete certainty when the Nigerian Arabic *maqāma* first appeared, one may assume that the indigenous production of the *maqāma* was underway by 2002, as demonstrated by circulation during this time of the manuscript of *al-Maqāma al-Awyuwiyya* by Imām Mas'ūd ibn 'Abd al-Ganiyy Adebayo (b. 1947), in Yorubaland, southwestern Nigeria.⁶⁸ In addition to Imām Mas'ūd's *al-Maqāma al-Awyuwiyya*, there are three other substantive *maqāma* works written by Nigerian scholars: *Maqāmāt al-Ilūrī* by Muḥammad al-Awwal ibn 'Abdul-Salām Ṣāhib al-Qur'ān al-Ilūrī (b. 1973), *Maqāmāt Ibn Yūsuf* by Aḥmad ibn Yūsuf Ajegunle (b. 1980), and *Kiswat al-'ārī fī maqāmāt 'Abd al-Bārī* by 'Abd al-Bārī Adetunji al-Ibādānī (b. 1948, officially known as Barihi Adetunji).

⁶⁸ A research completed in the department of Arabic University of Ilorin Nigeria in January 2003 has the *Oyowiyya* as its primary source, see: Musa Tijani Beekolari, "Dirāsa taḥlīliyya lil Maqāma al-Oyowiyya ta'lif al-Shaykh Mas'ūd 'Abd al-Ganī Adebayo" (BA Long Essay, Nigeria, University of Ilorin, 2003).

In addition to these four main works, new *maqāma* works can be identified in Nigeria today; some are works still in progress, while others are completed yet awaiting publication. For instance, an additional twenty *maqāmas* by Ajegunle are awaiting publication as part of the upcoming re-edition of *Maqāmāt Ibn Yūsuf*, which consists originally of thirty episodes.⁶⁹ Meanwhile, Adetunji has published two other collections of twelve and seven *maqāmas* titled: *al-Najm al-jārī fī maqāmāt ‘Abd al-Bārī* and *Nayl al-karāmāt fī fann al-maqāmāt* respectively, the copies of which I obtained at a very final stage of this project.⁷⁰ Outside the circle of the established *maqāma* writers in Nigeria (discussed below) are also new authors who are now presenting fascinating *maqāma* works. There are two unpublished *maqāma* manuscripts by Dauda Adeniji (1957-2021) titled *al-Maqāma al-Popowiyya*⁷¹ and Luqman Olalekan Alagunfon (b. 1996) titled *al-Maqāma al-Awlawraywiyya*.⁷² Abdul-Aziz Tunde Abdul-Qādir (b. 1970s), published in 2018 a collection of four *maqāmas* under the title *Maqāmāt al-Epewī*.⁷³ As will be seen in chapter two below, many disciples of *maqāma* teachers and writers are also trying their hands at the *maqāma*. The *maqāma* in Nigeria is not only a continuous literary endeavor, but also a living tradition with a vibrant renewed interest in it among the Yoruba Arabic-Islamic scholarly community.

What is striking about the emergence of the *maqāma* in Yorubaland is not the Arabic genre it resuscitated, but also the time, context, and location of this indigenous version. This allows us to critique widespread assumptions about the continued reception of the *maqāma*. The first is the notion that the *maqāma* genre ended with the premodern (and early modern) period of Arabic literature. Indeed, the revival of the *maqāma* while remaining true to its original classical form is something that scholars of modern Arabic literature have not anticipated. Rather they had declared some time ago that the *maqāma* era had come to an end, and that the genre was dead.⁷⁴ This conclusion was arrived at because there had been no serious engagement with the *maqāma* in modern Arabic literature since the late nineteenth century. The works closest to the genre composed in the twentieth century were no more than piecemeal

⁶⁹ More details below on the canonization of “fifty” in *maqāma* tradition.

⁷⁰ Barihi Adetunji, *al-Najm al-jārī fī maqāmāt ‘Abd al-Bārī* (Ibadan [Nigeria]: Baydakh Publishing and Media Hub, 2021); Barihi Adetunji, *Nayl al-karāmāt fī fann al-maqāmāt* (Ibadan [Nigeria]: Baydakh Publishing and Media Hub, 2022).

⁷¹ Dr. Dauda Rasaki Adeniji was a Nigerian Arabist. He was, before his death in March 24, 2021, a chief lecturer and head, Department of Arabic, Federal College of Education, Osiele, Abeokuta, Nigeria.

⁷² Luqman Alagunfon is an undergraduate student of Arabic at the Department of Arabic and Islamic Studies, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

⁷³ Abdul-Qadir teaches in his father’s *madrassa*, *Markaz al-‘ulum al-‘Arabīyya wa-l-Islāmīyya*, Alagbado, Lagos Nigeria, a branch of Markaz (see above). He has other write-ups in prose and poem, prominent of which are *Arājīz al-‘urfān fī tanshīt al-ikhwān* and *Bunāt al-Afkār*, his *Maqāmāt* is published as: Abdul-‘Azīz Yahyā Abdul-Qādir, *Maqāmāt al-Epewī* (Lagos [Nigeria]: al-Ma‘rūfa Press, 2018).

⁷⁴ Kilito, *al-Maqāmāt: al-sard wa-l-ansāq al-thaqāfiyya*, 5; Hämeen-Anttila, “An Old-Fashioned Genre – *Maqāma* in the 18th Century,” 11.

adaptations of the *maqāma* or its features in other genres that, in the words of Hämeen-Antilla, did not “grow out of the *maqāma* genre.”⁷⁵ The emergence of the Nigerian *maqāmāt* today brings the notion of the extinction of the *maqāma* into question, if not entirely negating it.

Secondly, the renewal of the *maqāma* was not foreseen to have emerged from a locality like Yorubaland, a non-native Arabophone land, where Arabic is used mainly for academic purposes of teaching and learning. One would have expected its re-emergence to have occurred in the Arab world, its home of origin. The rise of the indigenous Nigerian Arabic *maqāmāt* thus challenges the global narrative, not only in regard to the modern death of the *maqāma* genre, but also in regard to the development of modern Arabic literature as a phenomenon of the Arab world. As a result of this Arabo-centric narrative, Arabic literary works composed in Sudanic and sub-Saharan western Africa have been marginalized and not received the scholarly attention they deserve, despite the vibrant historical past of these regions as integral parts of the Islamic world. Recently some scholars have challenged this marginalization of Nigeria and West Africa by showing interest in indigenous Arabic literature.⁷⁶ By considering the Nigerian *maqāma* from a scholarly and literary perspective, I aim to further rectify the neglect of sub-Saharan west African Arabic literature and Arabic-Islamic scholarship emerging from this region as well as to make an important contribution to the world of *maqāma* and Arabic literature at large.

Dramatis Personae

There are various social actors responsible for the development of the *maqāma* as a literary work and are as well instrumental in the rise of its popularity in Yorubaland. They can be divided into two groups. The first group, the minor social actors, are those who engage with the Nigerian and classical *maqāmāt* in Nigerian society at a socio-educational level, rather than a direct literary one as authors; their minor or indirect contributions to the development of the Nigerian *maqāma* are based on their role as patrons, readers, students, and teachers. The largest constituents of this group are those who engage with the *maqāma* as teachers and their students. The second constituents of this group are educated readers, or aficionados, who hold *maqāma* in high esteem, and the patrons who supported the efflorescence of the *maqāma* in the society.

⁷⁵ Hämeen-Antilla, “An Old-Fashioned Genre – *Maqāma* in the 18th Century,” 11. Cf. the literary works mentioned in: Caroline Rooney, “The Contemporary Egyptian *Maqāma* or Short Story Novel as a Form of Democracy,” in *The Postcolonial Short Story*, ed. Maggie Awadalla and Paul March-Russell (London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2013), 111–32.

⁷⁶ For instance, see: Ousmane Kane, *Non-Europhone Intellectuals*, trans. Victoria Bawtree, CODESRIA Book Series (Dakar, Oxford: CODESRIA, 2012), 1–10; Fallou Ngom, *Muslims beyond the Arab World: The Odyssey of 'Ajāmī and the Murīdiyya*, Religion, Culture, and History (New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2016), 25–27. See also: Oludamini Ogunnaike, “Review of Beyond Timbuktu: An Intellectual History of Muslim West Africa, by Ousmane Kane,” *The Journal of Religion* 99, no. 3 (2019): 388.

Finally, we may also include in this group the tricksters and performers, who take their nicknames from characters featuring the classical *maqāma* and likewise adopt *maqāma* features in their acts.

The second group, who can be referred to as major social actors, include authors of the *maqāma*. They are the scholars who enrich the Arabic library of Yorubaland with this important literary corpus and bring to fore different kinds of memory, heritage, and tradition. Their lives, works and individual contributions are thus discussed below in a general overview of their respective *maqāmāt*. A stylistic, structural, and thematic exposition on their *maqāmāt* is given in Chapter Five.

I. The Imām and the Palace

The history of the modern Nigerian *maqāma* begins with Mas‘ūd ibn ‘Abd al-Ganiyy Adebayo (b. 1947), popularly known as Imām (or Imām Oyo). He received his elementary Arabo-Islamic education from scholars of his hometown Oyo, a town in the southwestern part of present-day Nigeria. In 1962 he obtained admission into the Markaz Madrasa⁷⁷ as an intermediate Arabic student. After completing his Markazi *tawjīhiyya*⁷⁸ or secondary education in 1969, he worked as a teacher in various private and public schools across Yorubaland until 1976, when he received a scholarship to study in Cairo’s al-Azhar University. After graduating from the al-Azhar in 1983 with a bachelor’s degree, he remained in Cairo additional nine years working as an announcer, translator, and editor for Cairo Radio, and taking courses on communication, publishing, and newscasting. After returning to Nigeria in the early 1990s, Adebayo began lecturing at the Zulaykha Abiola College of Arabic and Islamic Studies in Abeokuta and engaged in writing. His play, *Ustadh raghm anfih* (“A Teacher against His Will”), composed in Arabic in 2001, has been recognized as one of the foremost Nigerian plays in Arabic, and

⁷⁷ *Markaz al-Ta‘līm al-‘Arabī al-Islāmī* (Arabic and Islamic Training Center), founded by the encyclopedic historian and Islamic scholar, Shaykh Adam Abdullah al-Ilūrī (1917-1992) in 1952, is one of the leading Arabic schools in the Yorubaland today and has many students who are great Arabic writers and poets and who have produced many collections of poems. For more on the Markaz and its influence in the southwestern Nigeria see: Kazeem A. Omofoyewa, “Markaz and the Development of Arabic Language in South-Western Nigeria,” *Journal of Oriental and African Studies* 18 (2009): 267–76. For more on Shaykh Adam, his works and personality, see: Razaq ‘Deremi Abubakre, ed., *Shaykh Adam Abdullahi Al-Ilory in the Tableau of Immortality*, 2 vols. (Ilorin/Riyadh: Nigerian Center for Arabic Research in Riyadh, 2012); Hunwick, *ALA II*, 512–26; Stefan Reichmuth, “Islamische Bildung und Emanzipation der Muslime. Šaiḥ Adam al-Ilūrī, Nigeria, und seine Schriften,” *Die Welt des Islam* 30 (1990): 201–10. A personal encounter with him can be found in: Stefan Reichmuth, “Shaykh Adam as I Came to Know Him—Memories of an Islamologist,” in *Shaykh Adam Abdullahi Al-Ilory in the Tableau of Immortality*, ed. Razaq ‘Deremi Abubakre, vol. 2, 2 vols. (Ilorin/Riyadh: Nigerian Center for Arabic Research in Riyadh, 2012), 9–18.

⁷⁸ This is secondary level of Arabic studies used in the same meaning as *thānawiyya*.

displays the influence of his Egyptian friends, ‘Abd al-Jālīl al-Shalabī (d. 1995)⁷⁹ and his brother, ‘Abd al-Wadūd al-Shalabī (d. 2008) from whom he received personal instruction in writing drama and theater during his stay in Cairo.⁸⁰ In addition to his *Ustādh raghm anfih*, Adebayo has written various other religious and literary works. His *Āfāq al-dhahab: Majmū‘a min al-farā‘id al-adabiyya al-lughawiyya*, a treatise composed in 2005 on miscellaneous religious topics, emulates al-Zamakhsharī’s *Aṭwāq al-dhahab*.⁸¹ He has composed many poems in Arabic, that have yet to be collected in a *dīwān*. In 2005, he was selected the chief imam of Oyo, his hometown, which constituted a momentous event in his life. He later memorialized his struggle in attaining the post of imam in his *maqāma* writing. His *al-Maqāma al-Awyuwiyya* (hereafter, *Oyowiyya*), is a pioneering attempt to indigenize or, Nigerianize, the *maqāma* genre. His *al-Maqāma al-Fiktūriyya* (the *Maqāma* of Victoria), narrates his experience on a trip to Victoria Island, Lagos, Nigeria in 2004, the manuscript of which has yet to be found.⁸²

Fig. 1: Mas‘ūd ibn ‘Abdul-Ganiyy Adebayo, early 2020, Oyo, Nigeria. Photo: The Researcher

His *maqāma*, the *Oyowiyya*, an autobiographical account of his struggle for the position of chief imam of his hometown Oyo, an event that was fraught with power politics and lobbying

⁷⁹ For whom see: Nora Lafi, “Goldziher vu d’Al-Azhar: ‘Abd Al-Jalil Shalabi et La Critique de l’Orientalisme Européen,” in *Ignac Goldziher: Un Autre Orientalisme?*, ed. Céline Trautmann-Waller (Paris: Geuthner, 2011), 249–59.

⁸⁰ The work is an autobiographical play that relates how the author found himself in teaching profession without his planning. For more on Arabic plays in Nigeria, see: Zakariyau I. Oseni, “Prose and Drama in Nigerian Literature in Arabic: The Journey so Far” (Inaugural Lecture, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria., 2002). See also: Alagunfon, “Drama in Its Own Way: A Genealogy of Arabic Playwriting in Nigeria.”

⁸¹ For the rhetorical analysis of which see: Dirāsa badi‘iyya fī Kitāb Āfāq al-Dhahab lil-Shaykh Mas‘ūd al-Oyowī,” *Majalla al-Aasima* 5 (2013): 54–58.

⁸² All attempts to locate the manuscript of this *maqāma* proved abortive. Both his *al-Awyuwiyya* and *al-Fiktūriyya* are lost in their original writing. The text of the former, *al-Awyuwiyya*, is preserved in various research works from which I derive the version I use throughout this study. Unfortunately, no record or trace of the second, *al-Fiktūriyya*, could be found. I only rely on the information about this work found in reliable research works which mentioned it as his second *maqāma* episode. When I met him in March 2018, he verified that he wrote and circulated the manuscript of the *maqāma* but he himself has not been able to locate it again. The text of the first *maqāma* is contained in: Beekolari, “Dirāsa taḥlīliyya lil Maqāma al-Oyowiyya ta’līf al-Shaykh Mas‘ūd ‘Abd al-Ganī Adebayo.” Adetunji, “Dirāsa naqdiyya li-maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī wa-āthāruhā fī l-adab al-‘arabī al-nayjīrī.” and a brief discussion of both the *al-Awyuwiyya* and *al-Fiktūriyya* is in: Izzudeen Adetunji, “Maqāmāt Ṣāhib al-Qur’ān al-Ilūrī al-Nayjīrī: Dirāsa taḥlīliyya” (PhD thesis, Amman, World Islamic Science and Education University, 2014), 36–45.

(see the appendix). In the *Oyowiyya*, the narrator, al-Mufakkir ibn al-Wā'ī leaves Abeokuta⁸³ for Oyo with his friends, among whom is the imam-to-be, Shaykh Mas'ūd, the *maqāma*'s protagonist. The entourage's aim is to visit the Alaafin (King) of Oyo⁸⁴ and present him with their candidate for the vacant post of chief imam. Upon reaching the palace, the narrator begins by describing the architecture and setting of the magnificent palace.⁸⁵ He relates how the group is told to follow the official protocol for gaining access to the *Ṣāhib al-Jalāla*, his royal highness the Alaafin of Oyo. The group is permitted to enter the pavilion, where the queen welcomes them, assuring them of the king's availability in a symbolic gesture that the ruler has decided to have an audience with the group. Al-Mufakkir admires the queen's beauty, grace, and courtesy, which he extensively describes in a polished and ornate literary style. According to the traditional ritual of homage, the guests bow before the king in respect. Discussion between them and the king ensues regarding the position of the chief imam of Oyo. The king admonishes them to be patient, since the die has been cast, and an imam seems to have already been selected for the post. Hearing the vague comment by the king, al-Mufakkir proceeds to extol the virtues of his candidate, a strategy which displays the latter's curriculum vitae as a way to campaign for him. This is done with poetry, and the episode ends with them leaving the palace.

The aim of their visit – obtaining the post of imam for their candidate Shaykh Mas'ūd – ended in failure. The *maqāma* concludes with the protagonist being told to leave and wait his turn for when the position will vacant next. In fact, he is chosen four years later to be *al-Imām al-Akbar* (the highest-ranking imam) in the ancient Oyo town, the position which he holds till date. Adebayo, or the Imām, may be considered the pioneer of *maqāma* writing in Nigeria, although his total *maqāma* output consists of two independent episodes.⁸⁶

II. Ṣāhib al-Qur'ān and the *Ilūriyya*

Born to the Alalukurani (“the possessors of the Qur'an”) family, as they are famously called, hence his cognomen Ṣāhib al-Qur'ān, Muḥammad al-Awwal ibn 'Abd al-Salām al-Ilūrī (b. 1973) was the first to publish an entire collection of *maqāmāt* in Nigeria. His family is part of the so-called Makondoro,⁸⁷ an Islamic group of scholars who are known for their traditional Arabic schools, held in their own homes or in mosques. The Makondoro are generally known

⁸³ Abeokuta is one of the ancient towns in Yorubaland which was founded in early nineteenth century.

⁸⁴ Literally the owner of Oyo palace, this is the title of the Oyo King.

⁸⁵ As will be explained later, this hero-narrator combination in one personality is an innovative style in the *maqāma* which takes to *Maqāmāt 'alamatu l-dunya* of Abu al-Qasim al-Zamakhshari.

⁸⁶ See the appendix for a text of this *Maqāma* and its translation.

⁸⁷ For more on the group, see: Aliyu, “Transmission of Learning,” 127–33; Reichmuth, *Islamische Bildung*, 228–49; Rasheed Ajani Raji, “The Makondoro Muslims of Nigeria: Continuity Through Learning Strategies,” *Journal, Institute of Muslim Minority Affairs* 11, no. 1 (1990): 153–63.

for their conservative approach to Arabic and Islamic teaching and learning. There is no standard curriculum in this system of education, only an unofficial and unwritten list of books. Thus, one cannot specifically determine when a student will graduate from this kind of school. The time a student spends studying there depends on how long it takes for the student to master the set of books required to study. Students may spend up to ten years in such a school, depending on one's intellectual capacity. The students study Arabic texts by reading them from cover to cover, accompanied by oral translations in the local language by the teacher, yet with no additional commentary. Although the students don't memorize texts, they are still trained to memorize certain parts of the books they may need for public use such as in sermons. The students are trained to write the meaning of each word interlineally in their personal copies. Every student must, therefore, own his copy of a book. A daunting number of up to one hundred and fifty books must be read in a Makondoro school before one can graduate, and every book must be read from the beginning to the end, with the words' meanings clearly written on top of the Arabic text in the local language, mostly Yoruba, but any other language that will aid student's assimilation can also be used. Hausa and simple Arabic paraphrases might also be used.

After mastering the prescribed set of texts, students may leave the school to establish their own school, either in the front section of their parental house or at a nearby mosque.⁸⁸ A student departs with his personal copies of the books he learned from his master, which he uses for teaching his own students. It is from these books, together with the annotations scribbled in from his student days, that the graduate of the traditional school teaches, carrying on the intellectual heritage of his teacher before him intact. Since the schools are usually situated in the teacher's home, the students live together with their teacher and his family, constituting a tight-knit social unit.

Despite the absence of significant branches of Arabic studies in their studies, Makondoro students and their teachers have their way of understanding the Arabic language for their own purposes of oration and teaching. Since they take religious public oration through preaching more seriously than composing in Arabic, it may require extra effort for someone undergoing this kind of Arabic education to reach the latter goal. Indeed, speaking and communicating in Arabic is rare in a Makondoro school. Thus, it is difficult for the graduates to master Arabic fluently and they may not be able to communicate effectively with the language. No composition skills in both colloquial or literary Arabic writing are thus properly taught in this

⁸⁸ Sulaiman Adewale Alagunfon, "al-Lugha al-'arabiyya fī l-madāris al-ḥukūmiyya fī Nayjīriyā: Taṭawwuruḥā wa-mustaqbaluhā," *Majalla Al-Aasima* 7 (2015): 42–43.

kind of traditional school. Yet, the *Ḥarīriyya* holds the highest position in the Makondoro's unwritten curriculum.

Fig. 2: Shaykh Muḥammad al-Awwal ‘Abd al-Salām Ṣāhib al-Qur’ān (third from left) and the students of Dār al-Qur’ān, Alagbado, Ilorin, dressed in the school uniform. Photo: The Researcher (May 15, 2018).

The traditional Makondoro educational system as described above is important for understanding Ṣāhib al-Qur’ān’s intellectual background, as well as the motives lying behind his literary orientation (Chapter Two), and the public perception of him and his writings (Chapter Three). How did Ṣāhib al-Qur’ān acquire his Arabic writing skills if not from his traditional education? An external factor played an important role. After finishing his education at the Makondoro school in Ilorin, Ṣāhib al-Qur’ān moved to Kaduna to live with his uncle, another Makondoro scholar, where he met a Sudanese scholar, Muḥammad al-Marḍī, who taught in a private Arabic school. He befriended him and benefited immensely from his knowledge of Arabic. It is from al-Marḍī that he learned writing and speaking modern standard Arabic. Ṣāhib al-Qur’ān recounts his experience with al-Marḍī in the following way:

...I never studied with any “modern-oriented” scholars my entire life. But when I was in Kaduna, I met Shaykh Muḥammad al-Marḍī, a Sudanese, who was teaching at Abubakar Gumi College in Kaduna. He noticed that I read Arabic books and one day, he called out to me, asking: “What are you reading?” I showed him the Arabic book I had with me. He then said: let me teach you the *fannayn* (two disciplines) that will assist you in knowing all (the rudiments) of

the Arabic language. He then taught me *naḥw* (syntax) and *ṣarf* (morphology) for two months, and since then I have been learning everything else by myself.⁸⁹

Ṣāḥib al-Qur'ān is noticeably proud of his Makondoro background. He returned to Ilorin to establish his own school, the Dār al-Qur'ān, which operates from his residence. He nevertheless has introduced new features, while retaining the traditional Makondoro school structure. So, although he has moved slightly away from some of the conservative ways the Makondoro are known for, he has not changed the basic Makondoro outlook. Nevertheless, he has dispensed with certain traditional features, such as the wearing of big turbans blended with the use of school uniforms (see fig. 2 above), as well as the undefined and unlimited years of study, and other elements a typical Makondoro scholar may regard as alien to the system. Yet, he has not introduced a standardized curriculum and nor the partitioning of classes according to level in his school.

One of Ṣāḥib al-Qur'ān's significant departure from the traditional learning format is the organization of cultural and literary activities which encourage students to compose Arabic poems and prose works of a sound and sophisticated literary quality, including *maqālas* and *maqāmas*. Some of the writings of his students are published annually in the school magazine entitled, *Majalla Ṣawt al-Qur'ān*. The magazine features poems, articles, and other literary genres. Another innovation is the addition of new subjects, such as *naḥw* and *ṣarf*, in addition to the *maqāma*, especially those of al-Ḥarīrī, al-Hamadhānī, and the *Majma' al-baḥrayn* by al-Yāzījī, which constitute the most advanced level of the studies.

Ṣāḥib al-Qur'ān's *Maqāmāt al-Ilūrī* (hereafter, *Ilūriyya*) is to date the best known *maqāma* work in Nigeria and has been published numerous times. Its sixth edition published in 2017 includes a total of fifty episodes or individual *maqāmas*. When it was first published in 2003, it only had ten episodes or *maqāmas*. Aside the increase in the number of *maqāmas*, the new editions also present refined versions of the *maqāmas*, and, sometimes, certain *maqāmas* have been removed. So, newer editions may lack some important *maqāmas*, causing confusion in the setting of each episode and give additional content to some others. The *Ilūriyya* features accounts of Ṣāḥib al-Qur'ān's travels throughout Nigeria. The protagonist of the *Ilūriyya* is Abū al-Labīb, whose exploits are recounted by the narrator, Jibrīl ibn Khālid (see Chapter Five). Generally taking place in indigenous settings, the episodes are named after Nigerian cities and personalities, branches of Arabic studies, such as those on 'arūd (prosody, no. 30 *al-'arūdiyya*), *naḥw* (syntax, no. 29 *al-naḥwiyya*), or important Islamic sites, such as Mecca (no. 26 *al-Makkiyya*). Although their general structure takes much from al-Hamadhānī, the naming of

⁸⁹ Personal communication with Ṣāḥib al-Qur'ān, Ilorin on March 2018. Words in parenthesis are my intrusion.

protagonists deviates from the Hamadhānian way. Ṣāhib al-Qur'ān's style resonates with al-Zamakhsharī's *Maqāmāt 'alāmat al-dunyā*.⁹⁰ Whether the content of all these *maqāmāt* is closer to the *Hamadhāniyya* or the *Ḥarīriyya* remains to be ascertained, and will be explored in Chapter Five. Ṣāhib al-Qur'ān laid the foundation for modern Nigerian *maqāma* collections.

III. Ajegunle as the Ḥarīrī of Nigeria

The success of the *Ilūriyya* paved the way for further *maqāmāt* literature. In 2010, another scholar, Aḥmad ibn Yūsuf Ajegunle (b. 1980), published a thirty-episode *maqāma* collection. Born in Ajegunle Lagos state and raised in Ibadan Oyo state, Nigeria, Ajegunle is also a product of a traditional Makondoro Arabic school. His late father, Shaykh Yūsuf Ajegunle, under whom he began his elementary Arabic studies, was an important figure in the group associated with Shaykh Yusuf Agbaji (d. 1979), the founder of the Makondoro system. After learning to read the Qur'an from his father and the latter's sudden death, he was handed over to another Makondoro scholar with whom he completed his elementary Arabic education. He was later transferred to his uncle Shaykh 'Abd al-Karīm Abijuwon, who continued his education in Arabic and Islamic studies. After the death of his uncle and subsequent take-over of his uncle's school by the latter's *khalīfa* (successor), Ajegunle spent some years with him before embarking on a tour through many cities in southern Nigeria such as Ijebu, Port-Harcourt, Anambra, and Lagos. Ajegunle later returned to Ibadan, and he opened his own Arabic school which he continues to run and where he teaches the *maqāma* and other classics.

Like that of Ṣāhib al-Qur'ān, Ajegunle's Arabic school combines features from the traditional and modern systems, although not at the same level of modernization. For instance, Ajegunle's school does not organize literary activities as a way for students to further their literary prowess. Nevertheless, some of his students have become prolific writers. Ajegunle is one of the leading Arabic writers in Yorubaland today, and his travels had a significant impact on his *maqāmas* and other writings. Before publishing his *Maqāmāt Ibn Yūsuf* (hereafter, *Yūsufiyya*) in 2010, he wrote over fifty Arabic works, two-third of which are published. He is also a prolific Arabic poet whose numerous Arabic poems on topics of social and literary foci are collected in several diwans.⁹¹

⁹⁰ Abū l-Qāsim Maḥmūd ibn 'Umar al-Zamakhsharī, *Maqāmāt al-Zamakhsharī* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'ilmiyya, 1402).

⁹¹ What can be regarded as his first diwans is published in 2018/2019 which include a collection of prose and poetic works. He himself does not consider this a diwan and promises that another comprehensive diwan is forthcoming, see: Ahmad Yusuf Ajegunle, *al-Raḥīq al-makhtūm fī l-manthūr wa-l-manzūm* (Lagos [Nigeria]: Iswad, n.d.).

His *Yūsufiyya* is a collection of thirty *maqāmas* which include more than twenty *mu‘āraḍas* (contra-factions and emulations) on the *Ḥarīriyya*. In these *maqāmāt*, the author strives to imitate al-Ḥarīrī rather than to produce an original work. Nevertheless, it succeeds in indigenizing al-Ḥarīrī’s classical work, and as a truly Nigerian example of the *maqāma*, it addresses issues of social and religio-literary concern that are peculiar to Nigerian scholarly environment.

IV. Al-Ibadanī and the *Kiswa*

The last *maqāma* work considered in this study is that composed by Dr ‘Abd al-Bārī Adetunji al-Ibādanī (officially Barihi Adetunji), an academic and proprietor of a modern Arabic school. Adetunji’s training consists of a mix of both informal traditional learning with the modern system of education. Born in 1948, Adetunji began studying while a youth with traditional Ibadan scholars such as Shaykh Muḥammad Sādiq Folorunso (d. 1988) and Shaykh Mudaththir ‘Abd al-Salām (d. 1991), both former chief imams of the city. With these two scholars, Adetunji studied classical Arabic texts such as *Maqāmāt al-Ḥarīrī*, *Mukhtārāt al-shi‘r al-jahilī* (a collection of *mu‘allaqat* poems of pre-Islamic poets), *Jīmiyyat ibn Fodio*, *Mukhtasar al-khalīl* (Maliki jurisprudence), *Sirāj al-qāri’*, a commentary on al-Shāṭibī’s (d. 590/1194) primer on Qur’anic sciences, al-Zamakhsharī’s *Nawābiḡh al-kalim* and *Aṭwāq al-dhahab* and works on Prophetic praise (the so-called *Kutub al-madīh*), such as *Qaṣīdat al-burda*, the *Ḥamziyya* of al-Būṣīrī (d. 695/1295) and the popular *madīh* poem, *al-‘Ishrīniyyāt*.⁹² He also studied *Tafsīr al-jalālayn* together with the glosses of Aḥmad al-Ṣāwī (1175/1761-1241/825), the *Maqṣūra* and the *Mamdūda* of Ibn Durayd.⁹³

Adetunji also attended the Kharashi Arabic Secondary School which, established in 1945, is one of the earliest modern Arabic schools in Yorubaland. He graduated with distinction in 1970 and in 1977, he began attending the University of Ibadan where he earned a certificate in Arabic and Islamic Studies, with which he gained admission to the University of Jos, Nigeria in 1979 to study Arabic. He earned his BA in Arabic in 1982 and returned to the University of Ibadan for a Masters in Arabic and Islamic Studies (1983-1984) and Postgraduate Diploma in

⁹² For more on the influence of this poem in Nigeria, see: Rasheed Ajani Raji, “The Influence of the *‘Ishrīniyyāt* on Arabic and Islamic Culture in Nigeria” (PhD diss., Michigan, USA., The University of Michigan, 1982).

⁹³ For more on what constitute the intellectual and educational pursuit of Arabists in the whole of west Africa, Nigeria, and particularly Yorubaland, see chapter one below. see also: Kane, *Beyond Timbuktu*, 75–95; Aliyu, “Transmission of Learning,” 37–43; Hall and Stewart, “The Historic ‘Core Curriculum’ and the Book Market in Islamic West Africa”; Reichmuth, *Islamische Bildung*, 110–48; Abdul-Rahmon, “A Thematic and Stylistic Study of Arabic Poetry in Ibadan,” 1–82.

Fig 3: Dr. Barihi Adetunji at a public function in Ibadan, Nigeria, 2019. Photo: The Researcher

Education (1988). He then went on to earn a Ph.D. in Arabic from the University of Ilorin, Nigeria in 2004. Adetunji is the only *maqāma* author possessing a doctoral degree.

A scholar of high repute and a teacher *par excellence*, Adetunji has taught at various institutions of different levels, ranging from colleges of education to full-fledged universities. In 1989, he established a private school of Arabic, the College of Arabic and Islamic Studies (now Bari College of Arabic and Islamic Studies) in Olomi, Ibadan, Nigeria where he has been teaching since 2013, following his

retirement from teaching at government educational institutions. Many Nigerian academics have passed through his training, either via traditional Arabic schools, the public upper educational institutions where he taught, or in his own Arabic school. He is also a frequent public orator and a prominent member of the Council of the Ulama in Yorubaland. He was nominated the sixteenth Grand Mufassir of Ibadanland in April 2021.

Adetunji is also one of the most prolific Nigerian scholars in recent times. He has published over one hundred and fifty works, many of which are monographs and works in various genres of Arabic literature including plays, short stories, witticisms, novellas, sermons, and collections of poems. He publishes primarily in Arabic, except for a bilingual novel and play in both Arabic and English.⁹⁴ In 2017, he published two important books that mark a turning point in his career and enhanced his public profile. The first is the *Rawā'ih al-'anbar fī khuṭab al-minbar*, a collection of sermons modelled after the Friday sermons of Abdul-Raḥīm ibn Muḥammad ibn Nubāta (d. 374/984).⁹⁵ Ibn Nubāta's *Dīwān khuṭab minbariyya*⁹⁶ has been widely used by West African scholars for the *khuṭba* delivered on the pulpit every Friday over

⁹⁴ He alternates between the two languages in writing. For instance, his novella, *The Runaway Boy* first published in 2004, was initially written in English then redacted into Arabic by the author first with the title: *al-Walad al-farrār* and later under the title: *al-Walad al-hārib*. Whereas his play, *Baqā'un Muqaddar* (destined to survive) first published in 2005 in Arabic was redacted to English as *Education for every child* (An English play) in 2007.

⁹⁵ For whom see: M. Canard, "Ibn Nubāta," in *EP*, n.d. Not to be confused with the poet and writer Ibn Nubāta al-Miṣrī (686-768/1287-1366).

⁹⁶ For such *khuṭab*, see: Abdul Raḥīm ibn Muḥammad Ibn Nubāta, *Dīwān khuṭab Ibn Nubāta*, ed. Yasir M. al-Miqdād (Kuwait: al-Wa'y al-Islāmī, 2012).

the centuries.⁹⁷ He structures his *Rawā'ih* in accordance with the number of Fridays of the year using the Hijri oriented lunar calendar. He touches upon socio-cultural and political issues of concern to contemporary Nigerian society. Since its publication in 2017, the *Rawā'ih* has been widely acclaimed and used by imams in Yorubaland. Published at the same time with the *Rawā'ih* is his *maqāmāt* entitled *Kiswat al- 'ārī fī maqāmāt 'Abd al-Bārī* (hereafter, *Kiswa*).

The *Kiswa* is a collection of thirty *maqāmas* modelled after classical and modern *maqāmas*, prominent among which are the *Ḥarīriyya*, *Majma' al-baḥrayn* by al-Yāzījī and al-Zamakhsharī's *Maqāmāt 'alāmat al-dunyā*. With Abū Khālīd al-Ibādānī and al-Mujāhid ibn al-Hādī as protagonist and narrator respectively, the *Kiswa* creates the perfect type of homiletic, historical, and socio-cultural *maqāma* popular in Nigeria today, with topics ranging from social criticism to historical and pedagogical themes. The work has two conspicuous features: religious and linguistic. The majority of the *maqāmāt* in it are either sermons or verbal juggleries and philological acrobatics. The *Kiswa* takes no specific structure from any particular classical *maqāmāt*, but rather is a conglomeration of structures adapted from the various *maqāmāt* the author drew upon, including previously known Nigerian *maqāmāt*. Thus the *Kiswa* presents an inventory of styles found in the classical *maqāmāt* of al-Ḥarīrī, al-Hamadhānī, and al-Saraqusṭī (d. 538/1143)⁹⁸ as well as the modern *maqāmāt* of al-Yāzījī and Ṣāḥīb al-Qur'ān. It is thus the richest of all modern Nigerian collections.

Methods and Sources

The methodology of this study is transdisciplinary, drawing from socio-cultural and comparative literary studies. I combine textual analysis of the Nigerian *maqāmāt* with ethnographic field research and archival work that I conducted between 2018 and 2019 in Nigeria. I conducted a series of interviews and personal interactions with writers, teachers, and students of the *maqāma* in major towns in Yorubaland, Nigeria, namely Abeokuta, Ibadan, Ilorin, Lagos, and Oyo. This included observing *maqāma* classes in some Arabic schools, such as the Markaz Agege Lagos, the Dar al-Qur'an, Ilorin, and the Bari College of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Olomi, Ibadan. I also participated and facilitated key public events in propagating *maqāma* works in Yorubaland.

In order to ascertain the archival status of indigenous *maqāma* before the twenty-first century, I visited some libraries and archives in Nigeria, such as the Center for Arabic

⁹⁷ For more on *khuṭab*, see: Tahera Qutbuddin, *Arabic Oration: Art and Function*, Handbook of Oriental Studies. Section One, the Near and Middle East, Volume 131 (Leiden ; Boston: Brill, 2019).

⁹⁸ For whom, see: James T. Monroe, "Al-Saraqusṭī, Ibn al-Aṣṭarkūwī: Andalusī Lexicographer, Poet, and Author of *al-Maqāmāt al-Luzūmiyya*," *Journal of Arabic Literature* 28 (1997): 1–37; James T. Monroe, "Al-Saraqusṭī, Ibn al-Aṣṭarkūwī (Part II)," *Journal of Arabic Literature* 29 (1998): 31–58.

Documentation of the Institute of African Studies at the University of Ibadan, the Ibadan University Library, the Main Library of the University of Ilorin, the Centre for Ilorin Manuscripts and Culture of Kwara State University in Malete, the Arewa House's Centre for Research and Historical Documentation in Kaduna and the Arabic section of the National Archives in Kaduna. Chapter Three contains an examination of the book market by surveying the presence and circulation of published *maqāma* works at Arabic bookstores and other venues in Kano, Ilorin and Ibadan. I likewise engaged in conversation with local Arabic book publishers, marketers, and retailers to gain additional information and insight on their practices and attitudes.

I rely primarily on the four aforementioned Nigerian *maqāma* texts as the primary sources for this study. I have singled out these four texts because of their pioneering importance as well as the significant literary and social influence they have exerted on the Arabic-Islamic scholarly culture of Yorubaland and Yoruba society at large. Other sources include indigenous *maqāma* works still in manuscript form or in press. Other works are those I refer to as quasi-*maqāma*, for they are namely write-ups that do not fit the generic requirements of the *maqāma* although they are nevertheless presented as such by local scholars. Among these texts are short *maqālas* composed by students of the *maqāma*. Other works by *maqāma* writers and their disciples are also used as sources in certain instances.

I have collected voice-notes, video recordings (online through Youtube, and offline directly from the teachers and students) of *maqāma* classes in order to gain a direct and first-hand impression on how *maqāma* is taught as well as its appearance in public space. I have also used as ancillary sources instructional materials on the *maqāma*, such as curricula (virtual and hard copies) and lesson notes being used at various Arabic schools such as Markaz and Dār al-Kitāb Ilorin. Finally, since I myself am a product of the traditional-cum-madrassa system of Arabic-Islamic education, I draw from my own personal experience over the years in Yorubaland in learning, teaching, and editing *maqāmas* of both the classical examples and those of indigenous Yoruba authorship.

In order to understand the indigenization of the *maqāma* in Yorubaland, Nigeria, this study examines Yoruba Arabic-Islamic textual cultures as a product of its particular scholarly culture and literary traditions that have developed over recent decades. Some issues raised throughout this study, especially in Chapters Two and Three, are not peculiar to the *maqāma* but can also be applied more generally to Arabic literary works produced locally by scholars and students. On the other hand, I am careful not to overgeneralize by identifying literary-cultural aspects that are specific to the *maqāma* and are not applicable to other literary works.

Some clarification is necessary on how certain terms are applied in this study. “Scholar” is used in the sense of its local use in Yorubaland which literally translates to *alfa*. Traced to a Songhai origin, *alfa* is commonly used in the Islamosphere of Yorubaland in the general sense of *ulama*. No formal degree and criteria, however, are required for applying the term *alfa* or making claims to this status. Rather, popular perception determines who is included in the circle of *alfa* in Yoruba. Scholar likewise may be applied to teachers, writers and advanced students who are also capable of teaching the *maqāma* (see Chapter Three).⁹⁹

In transcribing the titles of *maqāma* episodes, I retain the Arabic article *al* to differentiate them from the titles of collections, which I do not add *al*. All titles formed with local words and nomenclatures are transcribed according to their Arabicized or Ajami forms. To avoid confusion, I transcribe the Ajami words in titles according to each author’s personal practice. Nigerian authors write local words in Arabic script in different forms due to the lack of a standard orthography for Ajami, based on their personal understanding.¹⁰⁰ Since some *maqāmas* carry the same titles across collections, this method of retaining author’s spellings can be additionally useful in differentiating chapters from different collections. A conspicuous example of this is the use of “Ilṛin” in the titles of the second *maqāmas* of the *Ilūriyya* and the *Yūsufiyya*, and in the third *maqāma* of the *Kiswa*. It is written in the *Ilūriyya* as *al-Ilūriyya*, in the *Yūsufiyya* as *al-Ilūriniyya* and in the *Kiswa* as *al-Ilawriniyya*.

Lastly, the general outlook of this study (especially Chapters Two to Four) suggests an anthropological enquiry. Although I am not an anthropologist, as an Arabist trained in Arabic language and literature, my approach and methodology has been greatly shaped by my training in cultural studies which draws much from anthropology. My examination of the *maqāma* in Nigerian-Yoruba society is ultimately based on my own experience, and involves to some extent the perspective of auto-ethnography by an amateur ethnographer.

⁹⁹ For the regional usage of the word in the sense of a lesser scholar, to use Levtzion’s term, see: Nehemia Levtzion, “Islam in the Bilad Al-Sudan to 1800,” in *The History of Islam in Africa*, ed. Nehemia Levtzion and Randall L. Pouwels (Ohio: Ohio University Press, 2000), 74. For its contextualized use in Yorubaland see: Adam Abdullah al-Ilūrī, *Nasīm al-ṣabā fī akhbār al-Islām wa-‘ulamā’ bilād Yūrubā* (Cairo: al-Maṭba’a al-Namūdhajiyya, 1987), 43. For its Songhai connection see: Stefan Reichmuth, “Songhay-Lehnwörter in Yoruba und ihr historischer Kontext,” *Sprache und Geschichte in Afrika* 9 (1988): 269–300.

¹⁰⁰ This orthographic problem of Yoruba Ajami scripts has been discussed by Amidu Sanni, see: midu Olalekan Sanni, “New Knowledge, Old Medium: The Yoruba Ajami of Southwestern Nigeria in the Factory of Learning” (Boston, 2017). See also: Amidu Olalekan Sanni, “Yoruba ‘Ajami’: From ‘Spurious’ Arabic to a Renewable Medium of Literacy” (Chicago, 2017); Isaac Adejoju Ogunbiyi, “The Search for a Yoruba Orthography since the 1840s: Obstacles to the Choice of the Arabic Script,” *Sudanic Africa: A Journal of Historical Sources* 14 (2003): 77–102.

Overview of Chapters

This study combines the approach of ethnographic field work (chapters 2, 3 and part of four) with that of comparative and literary analysis of Nigerian *maqāmas* and their classical models (Chapter Five). Chapter Two, “The Scholarly Setting,” describes the place the *maqāma* holds in the Arabic-Islamic scholarly environment of Yorubaland, Nigeria. It explores how Yoruba scholars engage with the *maqāma*, both classical versions as well as modern ones circulating in Nigeria, by examining the dissemination and development of the genre, as well as its influence in the literary tradition of Yoruba Nigerian society. Here, I analyze Nigerian reading culture in relation to the production of the Nigerian *maqāma* during the first two decades of the twenty-first century. This period coincided with a newly arising literary milieu in the scholarly and intellectual history of Nigeria, spanning the period of post-independence and the beginning of the twenty-first century. This new literary milieu is characterized by a blend of different written genres and reading traditions as well as divergent schools of thoughts on writing and reading in Arabic. This was also a seminal period of literary cross-fertilization, I argue, whereby modern versions of the *maqāma* as new literary products were nevertheless textually and contextually linked to the classical tradition. Modern readers thus continued to understand and read modern *maqāma* according to its classical model. The literary production of the *maqāma* in Nigeria is not only indebted to the *Ḥarīriyya* but remains deeply engaged with it, going beyond what Gérard Genette calls “affiliative writing.”¹⁰¹ Motivation, encouragement, and emotional attachment to the *Ḥarīriyya* have rendered *maqāma* writing in Nigeria a fruitful and successful cultural endeavor.

Chapter Three, “The Public Sphere,” is an exposition of the socio-cultural functions of *maqāma* writing, teaching, and learning in Yoruba Nigerian society. The indigenous Arabic *maqāma* in Yorubaland is not merely a literary product, but is also one with significant economic, social, and political facets and it continues to serve as a medium through which some scholars claim “agency” in society. It is also used as a socio-political tool by dignitaries in establishing their societal relevance, as we see with dignitaries who promote the *maqāma* by funding its publications or organizing a befitting luncheon for its public announcement. This

¹⁰¹ See: Gérard Genette, *Palimpsests: Literature in the Second Degree*, trans. Channa Newman and Claude Doubinsky, Stages, v. 8 (Lincoln and London: University of Nebraska Press, 1997). See also: Birgit Neumann, “Anglophone World Literatures and Transcultural Memory,” in *Handbook of Anglophone World Literatures*, ed. Stefan Helgesson, Birgit Neumann, and Gabriele Rippl, 1st ed., Handbooks of English and American Studies 13 (Boston: De Gruyter, 2020), 139–41.

chapter seeks to understand the reception of not only the writers but also their works through the socio-economic and spiritual functions of the *maqāma*.¹⁰²

Chapter Four focuses on the emotional dimensions of the *maqāma* in Nigeria. I argue that the strong emotional attachment to al-Ḥarīrī's work by both Nigerian scholars and the Arabic educated reading public provides an important context which shapes the reception of the newly emerging indigenous *maqāma*. In this chapter, I elaborate on how "emotions" play out in the Nigerian *maqāmāt* by looking at how they have been adopted as an "object of emotion" in themselves as well as a "vehicle" or "means" to portray various forms of emotion. In the society, the *maqāma* generates spontaneous emotions such as friendship (through love) and enmity (through anger, envy, and so on). Latter parts of this chapter explore the textual portrayal of emotions in the Nigerian *maqāma* texts and how the native Yoruba context influences their use of Arabic and the portrayal of emotion.

Building on the textual analysis in Chapter Four, I provide in Chapter Five, "The Old Way," a detailed overview of structures, forms, content, and sources of the Nigerian *maqāmāt*. Through a close reading, I demonstrate how authors prove their distinctiveness while maintaining the *maqāma*'s traditional features, or what we can call the "old way." Hämeen-Antilla's criteria discussed above are pivotal to this chapter as a lens through which I look at the Nigerian *maqāmāt* and their models in a comparative sense. The main question here is to what extent we can view the Nigerian *maqāmas* as part and parcel of the "art" of al-Hamadḥānī or al-Ḥarīrī? And what are their own specific traits in terms of literary and linguistic composition?

¹⁰² Cf. Appadurai's theory on social life of things, see: Arjun Appadurai, "Introduction: Commodities and the Politics of Value," in *The Social Life of Things: Commodities in Cultural Perspective*, ed. Arjun Appadurai (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986), 3–63.